

SCHOOL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
UNIVERSITY OF SIEGEN

PORSCHE ENGINEERING SERVICES

**Development of a Method for
Pre-calibrating LiDAR Sensors
Based on a Simulation
Environment**

MASTER'S THESIS

Mechatronics

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July 31st, 2023

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This Master's Thesis is handed in according to the requirements of the University of Siegen for the study program Master of Science (M. Sc.) Mechatronics.

Process period

February 1st, 2023 to July 31st, 2023

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Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that this Master's Thesis is my original work and only the indicated sources and resources were used. All references, ideas, and direct quotes taken from other sources and used in my thesis have been fully and properly cited.

Furthermore, it does not contain any material previously published or submitted, neither in whole nor in part, for credit of any other degree at any institution.

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Abstract

This master thesis report presents a pre-calibration method for LiDAR sensors using a simulation environment to achieve accurate calibration for highly autonomous driving. In autonomous vehicles equipped with multiple LiDAR sensors, precise alignment between these sensors is critical for reliable perception and decision-making. LiDAR sensors provide crucial 3D point cloud representations of the environment, and their accurate calibration is essential for correct spatial perception.

The proposed "Velo2cam Extrinsic Calibration Method" focuses on calibrating the extrinsic parameters between each LiDAR sensor and a master LiDAR, establishing the relative transformations between them. This method incorporates several adaptations and enhancements, including a novel "re-calibration step" that significantly improves calibration accuracy, particularly under challenging data conditions.

The thesis begins with a comprehensive exploration of the theoretical background of LiDAR sensors, covering topics such as point cloud representation, LiDAR sensor technology, point cloud processing, and the RANSAC algorithm utilized for calibration. Various evaluation metrics, such as the "similarity score" and "mean re-projection error," are carefully selected and justified for assessing calibration accuracy.

The evaluation process involves both simulation and real data experiments, providing validation for the proposed calibration method. The results demonstrate outstanding precision and accuracy, with a mean re-projection error of approximately 4 cm after calibration. These findings highlight the efficacy of the proposed method in achieving highly accurate and reliable calibration results.

The research significantly contributes to the field of LiDAR sensor calibration, enhancing the overall accuracy and reliability of highly autonomous driving systems. The methodological innovations, particularly the incorporation of the "re-calibration step," present a significant advancement in LiDAR sensor calibration, ensuring improved accuracy even in challenging data conditions.

Keywords: LiDAR sensor, calibration, RANSAC algorithm, performance metrics, point cloud.

Acknowledgements

I would like to extend my sincere gratitude to Professor Dr.-Ing. habil. Miguel Heredia Conde for his continuous support and guidance throughout this thesis. His expertise and insightful feedback have played a crucial role in shaping this research and its outcomes.

I am deeply grateful to my supervisors, Mr. David Hermann and Mr. Marcel Pelzer from Porsche Engineering Services, for their unwavering support and valuable contributions. Their expertise and dedication have been instrumental in the successful completion of this project.

Special thanks to Mr. Eike Wobken, my colleague at Porsche Engineering Services, for his assistance during the calibration tests. I also acknowledge the support of the entire team at Porsche Engineering Services for their valuable input during this research.

To my friends and family, thank you for your love, encouragement, and understanding throughout this journey. Your unwavering support has been a constant source of motivation.

Lastly, I express my gratitude to all the participants and volunteers who contributed to the real-world experiments. Your participation was invaluable to the success of this research.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Autonomous driving relies on precise environmental information to effectively determine the vehicle's trajectory. Mapping of the surroundings is a basic task in machine perception, which involves multiple sensor modalities such as cameras, LiDARs (Light Detection and Ranging), RADARs (Radio Detection and Ranging), IMU (Inertial measurement unit), GPS (Global Positioning System), etc. Presently, the primary objective in developing perception systems for automotive applications is to create architectures that synergistically combine diverse sensor modalities to enhance overall performance.

Among the various sensor options, vision systems are popular due to their ease of integration and their ability to provide appearance information [4]. Stereo-vision systems, which utilize a pair of cameras separated at a fixed distance, offer a cost-effective solution for obtaining depth information about the environment [10]. These systems provide dense 3D information that can be used to model the surroundings of the vehicle. However, one limitation of stereo-vision systems is their inability to function effectively in the absence of texture in the image.

Simultaneously, the remarkable development of 3D laser scanning technology has enabled its widespread use in both research and industry-driving applications in recent years [4]. Unlike vision systems, LiDAR range measurements are accurate and frequently provide information in a full 360° FOV (Field of View) [10]. Consequently, setups consisting of multiple LiDAR devices have become increasingly popular as they allow for the collection of high-resolution data using compact configurations.

The unique features of these sensory technologies make them suitable to be part of the same perception system, providing complementary information [17]. However, the collaborative operation of these sensor modalities requires accurate extrinsic sensor calibration to determine the relative positions and orientations of the sensors. This calibration process involves estimating the extrinsic parameters, which define the relative pose between the sensors, before data fusion and inference [3].

Despite the potential benefits, multi-modal calibration remains a non-trivial problem. Existing calibration methods suffer from issues such as the requirement for laborious ad-hoc environments or the lack of applicability to custom sensor setups. It is noteworthy that automotive setups require extraordinary accuracy in the calibration so that it is still valid for data association at long distances [4].

In the context of this research, the focus is on developing a method for pre-calibrating LiDAR sensors using a simulation environment. An existing calibration algorithm [4]

is adapted and applied to calculate the extrinsic transformations between different LiDAR sensor poses. The chosen algorithm demonstrates satisfactory performance across various sensor setups, including those with different properties such as point cloud density, FOV, and scan patterns [4].

In addition, a comprehensive study is conducted to assess this extrinsic calibration algorithm based on a simulation environment. This simulation-based approach provides a perfect ground truth of the transformation between sensors in space and establishes a fair benchmark for testing virtually unlimited sensor devices and relative poses. This methodology ensures the accuracy of the final calibration estimations.

By leveraging the simulation environment, this research facilitates the exploration of different scenarios and sensitivity analyses, providing insights into the robustness and limitations of the proposed pre-calibration method.

1.2 Problem Statement

Figure 1.1: Project JUPITER

The development of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) and autonomous driving technologies require extensive testing and engineering resources. In this context, Porsche Engineering Services has undertaken the JUPITER (Joint User Personalised Integrated Testing and Engineering Resource) research project, which utilizes the Porsche Cayenne E3 model as a platform for research and experimentation. The Cayenne E3 (Figure 1.2) is equipped with a diverse range of sensors, including cameras, stereo cameras, LiDAR, RADAR, GPS, IMU, and a high-end car CPU for sensor data processing. The sensor data is collected and integrated using ROS (Robot Operating System) middleware. The JUPITER platform provides a fully scalable and rapid prototyping vehicle, featuring a modular software architecture for ADAS and incorporating novel and state-of-the-art ADAS algorithms. It serves as a collaboration platform across various domains, enabling comprehensive testing and development of ADAS technologies.

Figure 1.2: JUPITER vehicle - Porsche Cayenne E3

Among the sensors utilized in the JUPITER vehicle, LiDAR sensors play a crucial role in perception tasks. The JUPITER platform incorporates three types of LiDAR sensors (1.1):

- **Blickfeld Cube1:** Positioned in the front of the vehicle, the Blickfeld Cube1 utilizes solid-state LiDAR technology based on MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems). It offers a FOV of 70° (H) x 30° (V) and enables configurable scanning lines, allowing for the selection of up to 50 lines to meet specific scanning requirements, and can capture 270,000 points/sec. The detection range for the Blickfeld Cube1 is up to 250 meters with 80% reflectivity.
- **Livox HAP:** The Livox HAP sensors are positioned on the sides of the vehicle. With a FOV of 120° (H) x 25° (V), they can capture over 452,000 points per second with their 64 lines. These sensors operate effectively within a temperature range of -40°C to 85°C and possess an IP67 rating. The maximum range is up to 200 meters, and the range is 150 meters at 10
- **Livox Horizon:** The Livox Horizon sensors are positioned on the front and rear of the vehicle. They offer a FOV of 81.7° (H) x 25.1° (V) and achieve a point capture rate of over 240,000 points per second with their 64 lines. The Livox Horizon sensors provide a detection range of up to 260 meters with 80% reflectivity.

LiDAR Sensor	FOV (H x V)	Point Capture Rate	Detection Range
Blickfeld Cube1	70° x 30°	270,000 points/sec	Up to 250m
Livox HAP	120° x 25°	452,000 points/sec	Up to 200m
Livox Horizon	81.7° x 25.1°	240,000 points/sec	Up to 260m

Table 1.1: Comparison of specifications of different LiDAR sensors

The Blickfeld sensor exhibits a unique channel-wise scan pattern, distinguishing it from other LiDARs. On the other hand, the Livox LiDARs, both HAP and Horizon models, introduce completely novel scan patterns that resemble Lissajous curves. Lissajous curves are a specific type of graph created by plotting a system of parametric equations. In the context of LiDAR scanning patterns, Lissajous curves appear as expanding infinity-shaped patterns that elegantly cross each other.

The figures 1.3, 1.4, and 1.5 below depict the scan patterns of these sensors. In these figures, the Lissajous curve-based scan patterns of the Livox LiDARs (1.3 and 1.4) can be observed, with the patterns resembling infinite shapes that intersect each other. In contrast, the Blickfeld LiDAR scan pattern (1.5) demonstrates its channel-wise scanning approach.

Figure 1.3: Livox Horizon LiDAR - Scan pattern

By making use of these LiDAR sensors in the JUPITER platform, tasks such as data collection and perception are made possible for ADAS and autonomous driving research. The accurate calibration between these LiDAR sensors is of paramount importance for the successful operation of the JUPITER platform. Some of these LiDAR sensors have little to no overlap area, which is a critical factor to consider for their calibration. The precise alignment and synchronization of these LiDAR sensors with little or no overlapping area enable reliable and accurate perception, forming the core focus of this master thesis. The proposed method for pre-calibrating LiDAR sensors, based on a simulation environment, aims to provide a robust and efficient calibration procedure to ensure optimal sensor fusion and enhance the overall performance of the JUPITER platform.

Figure 1.4: Livox Horizon LiDAR - FOV and scan pattern

Figure 1.5: Blickfeld LiDAR - FOV and scan pattern

1.3 Structure of the Work

This thesis comprises several chapters that comprehensively describe the adapted calibration algorithm, present the simulation environment, detail the experimental setup, analyze the results, and explore potential areas for future improvement.

Chapter 1 introduces the research topic, discussing the motivation behind developing a pre-calibration method for LiDAR sensors and its significance in enhancing accuracy and reliability in sensor fusion.

Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background, covering fundamental concepts of LiDAR sensors, extrinsic calibration in sensor fusion, an overview of existing calibration methods, and criteria for selecting an appropriate method.

Chapter 3 focuses on the development methodology and implementation details. It covers the *Velo2cam* extrinsic calibration method, along with the proposed adaptations and enhancements for the calibration algorithm. The chapter also describes the setup of the simulation environment and the selection and preparation of test data. Moreover, performance metrics are suggested and utilized to evaluate the algorithm in the conducted experiments.

Chapter 4 encompasses the experimental evaluation, including simulation and real data experiments. It presents the results and discusses the findings about the performance and limitations of the calibration algorithm.

Finally, the conclusion and future work are provided in chapter 5 which summarizes the key findings, addresses the limitations identified during the research, and suggests potential areas for further improvement in pre-calibration techniques for LiDAR sensors.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Fundamental Concepts

2.1.1 LiDAR Sensor Technology

Precise perception of the environment and objects within it is a fundamental requirement for highly autonomous driving. In highly autonomous vehicles, sensors are employed for environment perception. Among the commonly used sensors are RADAR, monocular cameras, and LiDAR [29].

Monocular cameras use passive image sensors to capture a two-dimensional projection of the environment. On the other hand, LiDAR and RADAR systems are active sensors, directly recording the 3D geometry of the environment without projection onto 2D and retaining depth information. LiDAR sensors offer higher resolution compared to RADAR sensors, enabling precise detection of even small objects at significant distances. Additionally, LiDAR sensors exhibit robustness against poor visibility conditions and can operate in complete darkness.

Active LiDAR sensors utilize eye-safe laser beams to achieve high-resolution perception of the environment. The wavelengths used in LiDAR sensors range from 850 nm to 1550 nm [42], depending on the design. These sensors operate based on the Time of Flight (ToF) principle. By emitting light pulses in a specific direction and measuring the time difference between transmission and reception of the reflected signals, the distance to the reflecting object can be calculated using the known speed of light. The components of a LiDAR sensor include a transmitter, a receiver, and a signal processor.

The transmitter emits pulsed laser signals in a specific direction, which are then reflected by objects in the environment. The receiver captures these reflections, digitizes them, and obtains distance values for individual laser beams based on the ToF principle, which involves evaluating the time difference between the transmission and reception of the signals. The measured values represent the distances to the reflecting objects from the LiDAR sensor [45]. Additionally, the intensity of the received signal provides information about the object's reflectivity.

The measurement data is associated with the original laser beam, parameterized by azimuth and elevation angles about a local reference coordinate system. This three-dimensional reference coordinate system is often centered in the middle of the sensor, allowing the complete parameterization of points in polar coordinates. To obtain a comprehensive and high-resolution representation of the environment, a single point is insufficient. Thus, LiDAR sensors employ mechanisms to vary the

transmission direction of the laser beam. Two main solutions are mechanical LiDAR and solid-state LiDAR [1].

Mechanical LiDAR utilizes motor-driven components to move the transmitter or deflect the beam using mirrors. This enables a high coverage of the FOV, with the azimuth reaching up to 360 degrees. However, mechanical LiDAR sensors have drawbacks, such as large space requirements, vulnerability to errors caused by production inaccuracies leading to vibrations, and reduced data quality [36].

In contrast, solid-state LiDAR refers to sensors that lack moving mechanical parts. The majority of mobile solid-state LiDAR sensors currently employ MEMS and optical phased array (OPA) technologies. MEMS sensors have a stationary transmitter, and the emitted beam is deflected by two micro-movable mirrors to adequately cover the FOV. OPA, on the other hand, enforces a defined transmission direction through optical phase arrays, modulating the beam's direction by influencing the phase shift of an array of emitters [35]. Solid-state LiDAR sensors offer advantages such as vibration-free operation, and compact and robust designs requiring less maintenance. However, the technology is still under development, and existing solid-state sensors tend to be more expensive than mechanical sensors [36].

Regardless of the technology employed, changing the direction of laser rays over time results in a collection of points that describe the surface and intensity of the environment within the sensor's FOV. This collection of points at a specific moment is referred to as a frame, and the rate at which frames are generated represents the frame rate. The sensor's FOV is partly determined by its design, often specified with vertical and horizontal opening angles. The angular resolution describes the spacing between individual rays used to generate the points within the FOV. It is important to consider the beam divergence, which refers to the fact that laser beams are not perfectly collimated but have a certain opening angle [45].

2.1.2 Point Cloud - Forms of Representation

In a point cloud, each point is typically represented by its Cartesian coordinates. Additional information, such as intensity and an ID corresponding to the laser beam ID, can be included for LiDAR sensors [7]. Point clouds can be represented in different forms, and they are often classified as organized or unorganized [34].

2.1.2.1 Organized Point Clouds

Organized point clouds have a structured and defined grid-like arrangement, commonly obtained from sensors that use structured light or depth cameras, such as TOF cameras and stereo cameras. These sensors provide depth information for each pixel or grid cell in a regular pattern. Organized point clouds maintain the laser ID for each point, typically within a single frame. When points from different frames are concatenated, the laser ID is lost, resulting in an unorganized point cloud. Key characteristics of organized point clouds include:

- Regular grid structure: Points are arranged in rows and columns, forming a 2D grid that represents the 3D scene.
- Image-like representation: The point cloud can be visualized similarly to an image, with each pixel corresponding to a 3D point.
- Common formats: Organized point clouds are often represented in formats like PCL (Point Cloud Library) PointCloud or Kinect-style depth maps.

2.1.2.2 Unorganized Point Clouds

On the other hand, unorganized point clouds lack a structured grid-like arrangement and are obtained from sensors like LiDAR or photogrammetry techniques, capturing points at arbitrary positions in 3D space. Characteristics of unorganized point clouds include:

- Random point distribution: Points have no inherent order or structure and are scattered in 3D space.
- Point connectivity: There is no immediate relationship between neighboring points, and the density of points can vary across the scene.
- Common formats: Unorganized point clouds are typically represented in formats like PCL PointCloud or the widely used .PLY format.

2.1.2.3 Applications of Organized and Unorganized Point Clouds

Applications of organized and unorganized point clouds differ based on their characteristics:

- Organized point clouds are well-suited for tasks such as 3D reconstruction, mapping, and surface analysis, where the regular structure simplifies data processing and interpolation.
- Unorganized point clouds are commonly used in applications like object detection, robotics, and scene understanding, where the 3D data is more complex and requires more sophisticated algorithms for processing.

Point cloud processing software libraries often classify point clouds based on indexing rather than laser ID, considering the preferred form of representation for faster iteration or efficient storage [37] [31].

2.1.3 Point Cloud Processing

Raw point clouds captured by LiDAR sensors often require processing to extract meaningful information [7]. Point cloud processing involves filtering, structuring, and extracting features.

- **Filtering:** Point cloud filtering techniques are used to remove noise and outliers from the raw data. Methods such as voxel representation and statistical filtering can achieve cleaner point clouds. Voxel downsampling divides the point cloud into individual grid points called voxels, allowing for noise reduction and preservation of structural information. Statistical filtering approximates the noise as normally distributed shot noise and removes points that fall outside a defined interval of the average distance to their neighboring points [39].
- **Structuring:** Structuring point clouds involves organizing them in a way that facilitates efficient processing. Range images and data structures like KD trees are commonly used for this purpose. Range images represent the point cloud as a two-dimensional image matrix, where each pixel corresponds to a point with distance and intensity values [47]. Stereographic projection is used to calculate the image coordinates of a pixel based on its associated point's polar coordinates. Classical image processing algorithms can be applied to range images, and the results can be back-projected into the point cloud, providing more information than the raw data. KD trees are tree structures that enable efficient local search operations in large point sets, allowing for faster retrieval of points based on their neighborhood [27].
- **Features:** To capture geometric and semantic properties shared among neighboring points, features are extracted from the point cloud [39]. Keypoint detection aims to find distinct points in the point cloud, while feature descriptors provide descriptions of these keypoints, encoding their relationship with surrounding points [21] [49]. Keypoint detection and feature extraction together constitute a representation of the distinctive features of a point cloud. Normal estimation approximates the local geometry of a point by fitting it to a plane and describing it with a normal vector perpendicular to the plane. By detecting keypoints, computing feature descriptors, and estimating normals, point clouds can be enriched with additional information for analysis and interpretation [43].

2.1.4 Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC)

In point cloud processing, it is often necessary to generate models from existing point data. The RANSAC algorithm [18] is commonly used for this purpose, allowing the robust fitting of models, such as straight lines or planes, to a set of points. RANSAC is particularly useful in point cloud data processing due to its robustness against outliers [2].

The RANSAC algorithm operates by randomly selecting a subset of points from the point cloud to create a model. This model is then used to evaluate the remaining points in the cloud, determining whether they are inliers (points that fit the model) or outliers. The process is iterated to find the model with the highest number of inliers. Figure 2.1 illustrates the RANSAC algorithm in two dimensions, where two possible models are generated. In this example, the model from cd is rejected as it does not fit the majority of the points, while the model from ab is accepted with

convergence. It is important to note that the RANSAC algorithm can be extended to handle multidimensional data, including three-dimensional data, allowing for the estimation of models in three-dimensional space.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the RANSAC algorithm’s basic operation principle, adapted from [22]

By iteratively selecting subsets of points and evaluating models, RANSAC enables accurate modeling even in the presence of outliers, making it suitable for calibration algorithms that require robustness and accuracy [2].

2.1.5 Registration

Point clouds are often represented in Cartesian coordinates referenced to a specific coordinate system. In the case of point clouds from LiDAR sensors, the reference coordinate system is typically the sensor coordinate system, located at the center of the sensor [14].

When working with data from multiple sensors or coordinate systems, there may be unknown differences in the relative positions of these coordinate systems. To align point clouds from different sensors or coordinate systems, a process called registration is performed. Registration aims to find an optimal transformation that minimizes the differences between the coordinate systems.

Different approaches exist for registration, including geometric approaches, probabilistic approaches, and learning-based approaches [26]. Some widely used registration methods include:

- **Iterative Closest Point (ICP):** ICP is a widely used geometric registration method that iteratively aligns point clouds by minimizing the distances

between corresponding points in the clouds [8]. It iteratively refines the transformation until convergence, providing an accurate alignment.

- **Umeyama Registration:** Umeyama registration [41] is a geometric registration method that seeks to find an optimal transformation by minimizing the least squares error between corresponding points in the clouds. It provides an optimal rigid transformation solution.

These registration methods play a crucial role in aligning point clouds, enabling the accurate fusion of data from multiple sensors or coordinate systems. In the context of this thesis, these two registration methods are utilized in the algorithm for LiDAR sensor calibration.

2.2 Extrinsic Calibration in Sensor Fusion

Extrinsic calibration plays a crucial role in sensor fusion by determining the rigid transformations, including 3D rotation and translation, between the coordinate frame of a sensor and other sensors or reference frames. The accuracy of extrinsic calibration is essential for accurate sensor fusion, as it ensures that the data from multiple sensors are properly aligned and can be effectively combined.

In the context of sensor systems with LiDARs, there are two main categories of calibration methods: motion-based methods and target-based/appearance-based methods [11].

- **Motion-based methods:** Motion-based methods estimate the relative poses of sensors by aligning an estimated trajectory from independent sensors or fused sensor information [44]. One commonly used motion-based calibration technique is hand-eye calibration, which is frequently employed in Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) systems. The hand-eye calibration problem is typically formulated as $AX=XB$, where A and B represent the motions of two sensors, respectively, and X denotes the relationship between the two sensors [25] [44]. By solving this equation, the relative poses of the sensors can be determined.
- **Target-based or appearance-based methods:** Target-based or appearance-based methods rely on specific targets with distinguishable geometric features, such as a checkerboard pattern [11]. A calibration board is a physical object that is captured simultaneously by both sensors. Recognizable points on the calibration board serve as correspondences between the sensors. By capturing images or point clouds of the target from different sensors and establishing point-to-point correspondences, the extrinsic transformations between the sensors can be estimated.

Motion-based calibration methods are well-suited for dynamic environments where the sensors are in motion and can capture diverse scenes. These methods can provide accurate extrinsic calibration results without requiring specific targets, making them more versatile in various scenarios. However, motion-based methods may be more computationally intensive and require careful trajectory estimation.

Target-based methods, on the other hand, are particularly useful in controlled environments where the targets can be strategically placed and observed by the sensors. These methods provide a direct and explicit calibration process by leveraging the known geometric features of the targets. However, they are limited to scenarios where the targets are visible and correspondence points can be reliably established.

The choice between motion-based and target-based calibration methods depends on several factors, including the application requirements, available sensor data, sensor stack or setup, and environmental conditions. Consideration should be given to factors such as desired calibration accuracy, computational complexity, ease of implementation, and feasibility of deploying specific targets. Selecting the most appropriate extrinsic calibration method enables accurate sensor fusion, facilitating the integration and synchronization of data from multiple sensors in a coherent and consistent manner.

2.3 Overview of Extrinsic Calibration Methods

The calibration of extrinsic parameters for sensors of different modalities has been extensively studied in the fields of robotics and automotive platforms. Calibration methods have been developed for camera-to-range and multi-sensor systems involving LiDAR or cameras.

Traditionally, calibration has been performed in a controlled environment before regular operation. Manual annotation has been a common approach, but automatic methods are gaining interest due to the prevalence of miscalibrations in robotic platforms [38]. Calibration targets, such as triangular boards [12], polygonal boards [33], spheres [5], or boxes [16], are used to establish correspondences between data acquired from different sensors. Planar targets like checkerboards [4] or targets with visual features like QR markers [13] are commonly used when monocular cameras are involved alongside LiDAR sensors. These targets allow the retrieval of scene geometry by inferring the missing scale factor.

As high-resolution 3D LiDAR sensors gain popularity, research focus has shifted towards their calibration [20]. Various methods have been proposed, including single-shot calibration with planar checkerboards, circular feature detection on calibration patterns, and registration of reference points in both LiDAR and image data. However, existing methods are mostly designed for higher-resolution LiDAR scanners, and calibrating low-resolution LiDAR scanners presents unique challenges.

Some approaches avoid the use of artificial calibration targets and instead utilize features in the environment. These target-less calibration methods extract linear features from natural scenes [23] or leverage the ground plane and obstacles in traffic environments [48], exploiting coplanarity and orthogonality of scan points on orthogonal planes [9]. Some methods use planar surfaces arranged in a wall corner shape [50] or employ adaptive surface normal estimation techniques for multimodal LiDAR calibration [30]. These emerging methods aim to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the calibration process by adapting to different scenarios and providing automated solutions [44]. Certain methods are semi-automatic, performing

registration on user-selected regions. Recent advancements include the use of deep convolutional neural networks for continuous online calibration and self-supervised calibration frameworks [46].

Focusing on multi-LiDAR sensor calibration, various methods have been developed to determine the relative pose of LiDAR sensors with respect to each other. Most of these methods have specific requirements and common assumptions, including the incorporation of additional sensors like IMUs, GPS, or cameras, user initialization steps, specific calibration target objects, and assumptions about planar vehicle motions or LiDAR sensors lying on the same plane.

However, calibrating multiple 3D LiDARs with little or no overlap in their FOV remains challenging, and some approaches involve using additional sensors to establish correspondences among the scan data. By synchronizing data from bridge sensors and applying appropriate calibration algorithms, it becomes possible to accurately estimate the extrinsic parameters between the LiDAR sensors that need to be calibrated, even in the absence of overlapping areas. The choice of additional sensors depends on the specific setup and requirements of the calibration process, with commonly used sensors including cameras, IMUs, GPS systems, and other LiDAR sensors. Cameras provide visual information that complements LiDAR data and aids in feature detection and matching. IMUs provide motion and orientation information, helping account for vehicle movements and sensor motions during calibration. GPS systems provide global position information that allows for correcting the drift of inertial sensors and assists in aligning the LiDAR data with the environment. LiDAR sensors provide point clouds of the surrounding area and, if placed correctly, can act as bridges, creating a common overlap area with the other LiDAR sensors to be calibrated.

2.4 Criteria for Method Selection

To simplify the calibration problem of multiple LiDAR sensors with little or no overlap area on the JUPITER vehicle, a bridge sensor (a reference LiDAR) is introduced [32]. The objective is to establish a common overlap area between each LiDAR sensor and the reference LiDAR. This simplifies the calibration problem to the calibration of two LiDAR sensors facing a common calibration target. Further details about the selected bridge sensor are provided in subsequent chapters.

In the process of selecting a calibration method to calculate the extrinsic transformation between two LiDAR sensors, certain criteria must be considered. The goal is to enable the comparison of point clouds generated by these sensors, despite their varying properties such as scan patterns, point cloud density, and FOV. The objective is to adapt existing algorithms rather than develop new ones, to minimize the distance between point clouds acquired by different LiDAR sensors. To effectively select and adapt an existing calibration method, the following requirements have been identified based on the sensor setup, conditions, and company policies of Porsche Engineering Services, as well as technical aspects:

- **Adaptable to Diverse Sources:** The calibration method should exhibit flexibility to accommodate variations in point cloud density, FOV, and scan patterns of different LiDAR sensors.
- **Globally Optimal Transformation and Calibration Accuracy:** The selected calibration approach should aim at finding a transformation that globally minimizes the distance between input point clouds. It should strive to identify the optimal solution while minimizing the risk of falling into a local minimum of the cost function, ensuring the highest possible calibration accuracy.
- **Minimum Preparation Effort (Pre-processing):** The calibration process should involve minimal pre-processing of data. It should be efficient and not heavily rely on prior knowledge of the scene or the nature of the data.
- **Degree of Automation:** The chosen method should possess a certain level of automation, allowing for efficient calibration without excessive manual intervention. This automation would streamline the calibration process and enhance its usability.
- **Practicability (Feasibility):** The calibration method must be practical and feasible to implement in real-world scenarios. It should take into consideration the limitations and constraints of the hardware and software used.
- **Time Efficiency and Computational Complexity:** Time efficiency and computational complexity are critical factors in the calibration process. The selected calibration method should aim to achieve accurate results within a reasonable timeframe, optimizing the overall efficiency of the procedure. Striving for a calibration method that balances accuracy and efficiency is crucial for practical applications. It is essential to consider the trade-off between the quality of calibration and the computational resources required for the calibration process.
- **Ease of Integration:** The ease of integrating the calibration method is crucial, emphasizing the importance of selecting a method that can be readily incorporated into existing systems or frameworks, minimizing development efforts and potential complications related to interfacing with current systems. For instance, a calibration approach that seamlessly integrates with common LiDAR processing software or hardware setups would be highly advantageous in practical applications.

By considering these criteria, a suitable calibration method can be chosen that effectively addresses the specific challenges of extrinsic calibration between two LiDAR sensors.

3 Development of the Methodology and Implementation

3.1 Velo2cam Extrinsic Calibration Method

The *Velo2cam* Extrinsic Calibration Method [4] is utilized to estimate the rigid-body transformation that defines the relative pose between a pair of sensors. These sensors can include LiDAR scanners, monocular cameras, or stereo cameras, in various combinations.

The transformation between the pair of sensors can be defined by a vector of six parameters $\vec{\theta} = (t_x, t_y, t_z, r_x, r_y, r_z)$, which describe the position and rotation of one of the devices in the reference frame attached to the other one [4]. The rotations around the axes (r_x, r_y, r_z) are commonly referred to as roll, pitch, and yaw angles, respectively.

Parameters in $\vec{\theta}$ unambiguously define a matrix T that can be used to transform a 3D point between the two coordinate systems [10]. For instance, in a LiDAR-monocular setup, a point p_M in the monocular coordinate system M can be transformed into LiDAR space represented by coordinate system L , using $p_L = T_{LM}p_M$ once the transformation matrix T_{LM} is built. It should be noted that, in this particular case, the parameters $\vec{\theta}_{LM}$ used to obtain T_{LM} express the pose of the coordinate system M with respect to coordinate system L .

The proposed approach automatically obtains the transformation from the data obtained by the sensors to be calibrated. A custom-made planar target is employed to provide features that are detected and paired between data coming from the different sensors [4]. The calibration pattern has geometric and visual characteristics that enable the estimation of keypoints in LiDAR, stereo, and monocular modalities [10]. It consists of four circular holes that exploit geometrical discontinuities in LiDAR and stereo point clouds. Additionally, four ArUco markers [19] are placed near the corners to extract 3D information from monocular images.

This method does not impose strict limitations on the relative pose between the devices, making it suitable for sensor setups with significant translation and rotation parameters. However, two reasonable constraints are necessary. Firstly, there must be an overlapping area between the sensors' FOV where the calibration target is placed. Secondly, the holes in the pattern must be visible in the data captured by the sensors [4], especially in the case of range data calibration, where each circle must be represented by at least three points. In the case of multi-layer LiDAR sensors, this means that at least two scan planes intersect with each of the circles

[10]. Additionally, the intrinsic parameters of each device (such as focal lengths or stereo baseline) are assumed to be known.

The calibration procedure is designed to be conducted in a static environment. While a quick estimation of the extrinsic parameters can be obtained with a single pose of the target, the accuracy and robustness of the results can be improved by accumulating several positions.

The calibration algorithm consists of two stages [4]. The first stage (Section 3.1.1) involves segmenting the calibration target and localizing the reference points in each sensor’s coordinate system. This stage varies depending on the sensor type, with specific preprocessing steps for LiDAR, stereo, and monocular data as shown in Figure 3.1. The result is a set of 3D points representing the centers of the target holes.

Figure 3.1: Pipeline of the *Velo2cam* calibration method, adapted from [4].

In the second stage (Section 3.1.2), the reference points from both sensors are used to find the optimal transformation parameters that align the points. The registration problem is treated as a multi-objective optimization, and a point association procedure is developed to handle unordered reference points. The resulting transformation matrix provides the relative position parameters between the sensors.

3.1.1 Target Segmentation

The first stage aims to localize the calibration target in the data captured by each sensor as shown in Figure 3.3(a). The measurements at this stage are relative to the local coordinate system of the respective sensor [4]. Three different variants of the procedure are proposed, one for each sensor type, as the features used to localize the pattern differ for each modality [10]. The output of this stage is a set of four 3D points representing the center of the holes in the target, in local coordinates [4]. These points will later be used to establish correspondences between the different data sources.

Figure 3.2: Adjustable pass-through filters using dynamic reconfigure in ROS, adapted from [4]

3.1.1.1 LiDAR Data Preprocessing

Data from a LiDAR scanner [28] is assumed to be represented as a 3D point cloud, with measurements distributed into different layers, as typical in mechanical devices based on rotating mirrors [4]. Before feeding the data to the segmentation procedure, pass-through filters are applied in the three cartesian coordinates to remove points outside the area where the target is to be placed, avoiding spurious detections that could slow down the processing. The limits of the pass-through filters (Figure 3.2) must be set according to the location and size of the sensors' overlapping area [10]. The resulting cloud P_1 as shown in Figure 3.3(b), must represent both the calibration target and the points behind it visible from the LiDAR through the holes [4].

To segment the holes in the pattern, the points representing the edges of the target are extracted using depth discontinuities. For the LiDAR modality, the method from [28] is followed to find depth discontinuities. Each point in the cloud, $\vec{p}_i \in P_1$, is assigned a magnitude representing the depth gradient with respect to their neighbors:

$$\vec{p}_{i,\Delta} = \max(\vec{p}_{i-1,r} - \vec{p}_{i,r}, \vec{p}_{i+1,r} - \vec{p}_{i,r}, 0) \quad (3.1)$$

where $\vec{p}_{i,r}$ is the range measurement given by the LiDAR sensor for point $\vec{p}_i$, and $\vec{p}_{i-1}$ and $\vec{p}_{i+1}$ are the points adjacent to $\vec{p}_i$ in the same scan plane. Then, all points $\vec{p}_i$ with a discontinuity value $\vec{p}_{i,\Delta} < \delta_{\text{discont},L}$ are filtered out, resulting in P_2 . This procedure assumes that measures from rays passing through the holes exist, and they collide with some solid located behind the target within the measurement range of the LiDAR.

3.1.1.2 Stereo Data Preprocessing

When one of the sensors to be calibrated is a stereo-vision system, data processing starts by converting the raw image pair into a 3D point cloud using a stereo matching procedure [10] [4]. Pass-through filters are applied, and a Sobel filter is used for edge segmentation [24].

3.1.1.3 Range Data

The steps for segmenting the pattern holes in the preprocessed point clouds are common for both LiDAR and stereo modalities, aiming to estimate the 3D location

Figure 3.3: Front facing LiDAR - Unfiltered and filtered point cloud

of the hole centers in sensor coordinates.

- **Plane Segmentation:**

Firstly, a plane segmentation using RANSAC is applied to P_1 , the resulting cloud from pass-through filters, to obtain a plane model π representing the calibration target [4]. The model's accuracy is ensured by using a tight RANSAC threshold δ_{plane} , removing extraneous points, and requiring the plane to be roughly vertical in sensor coordinates, with a tolerance α_{plane} . Frames without a suitable plane model are discarded.

The plane model π is then used in P_2 , the cloud representing the pattern edges, to remove non-plane points using a threshold δ_{inliers} . The resulting cloud P_3 contains only the edges of the calibration target, including the outer borders and holes as shown in Figure 3.4(a).

- **Transformation to 2D Space:**

As all remaining points belong to the same plane, dimensionality reduction is performed by transforming P_3 so that the XY-plane coincides with π and projecting all the 3D points onto π . The resulting cloud P_4 contains points in 2D space [4].

- **Circle Segmentation:**

Next, 2D circle segmentation is applied to extract a model of the pattern holes in P_4 . The segmentation is performed iteratively, finding the most supported circle, removing its inliers, and repeating until the remaining points are insufficient to describe a circle. At least four circles need to be found for the procedure to continue; otherwise, the frame is discarded. Inliers are determined using a threshold δ_{circle} , and only circles within a radius tolerance δ_{radius} are considered.

The identified circle points are checked for geometric consistency with the pattern dimensions. Centers are grouped into sets of four, and the dimensions of the formed rectangle (diagonal, height, width, and perimeter) are compared

with theoretical values, with a tolerance $\delta_{\text{consistency}}$ expressed as a percentage deviation [4]. Frames with no or multiple sets passing the check are discarded to eliminate spurious detections.

Figure 3.4: LiDAR data preprocessing - Edge detection and circle centers

Once the holes are correctly identified, their centers are converted back to 3D space in sensor coordinates, forming the cloud P_p [4]. It is important to note that P_p must contain exactly four points as shown in Figure 3.4(b).

3.1.1.4 Monocular Data Preprocessing

If the sensor to be calibrated is a monocular camera, the extraction of the reference points requires the detection of ArUco markers [4], which provide the cues necessary to retrieve the geometry of the target [19] [10].

ArUco markers are synthetic square markers made of a black border and an inner binary matrix designed to allow its unequivocal identification [4]. The markers' 3D pose is estimated, and the points representing the center of the reference holes are extracted.

3.1.1.5 Point Aggregation and Clustering

At the end of the segmentation stage, two point clouds, P_p , are generated, each representing the 3D location of the reference points (centers of target holes) [4] for a single static scene in the coordinate frame attached to the respective sensor. The robustness of the algorithm is further increased by applying the segmentation step repeatedly and accumulating the results in two ways.

- **Accumulation Over Several Data Frames**

To increase reliability, the points from P_p are accumulated over a series of N consecutive data frames, resulting in a cumulative point cloud denoted as P'_p . Euclidean clustering is then performed on this accumulated cloud. If more

than four clusters are identified, the data is deemed unreliable and not used for the registration process. However, if four or fewer clusters are detected, the centroids of these clusters, stored in the resulting point cloud P_c , provide a consolidated estimate of the reference point locations. The clustering parameters, such as the cluster tolerance (δ_{cluster}), minimum cluster size ($N_{\text{cluster,min}}$), and maximum cluster size ($N_{\text{cluster,max}}$), depend on the number of iterations considered. $N = 30$ yields satisfactory results within a reasonable timeframe.

- **Accumulation Over Several Target Poses**

To enhance the accuracy of the estimation, multiple reference points are considered by repeating the segmentation procedure for M different poses of the calibration target in relation to the sensors. For each pose, the segmentation process is executed, resulting in point clouds denoted as P_{cM} . These point clouds representing the estimated reference points are then accumulated into a single cloud, denoted as P'_c , which contains a total of $4 \times M$ reference points available for the subsequent registration stage [4]. The selection of poses ensures that the resulting reference points are not coplanar and span a wide range of distances from the sensors. By incorporating this additional constraint, ambiguities are resolved, leading to an improved overall calibration quality.

3.1.2 Registration

Following the segmentation stage, the estimated 3D locations of circle centers in sensor coordinates are represented by two point clouds, denoted as P'_{Xc} and P'_{Yc} obtained from arbitrary sensor modalities X and Y . The goal of the registration step is to find the optimal parameters $\hat{\theta}$ that result in the best alignment between the reference points from both sensors when the resulting transformation $\hat{T}$ is applied [10]. The registration problem is viewed as a multi-objective optimization with a composition of $4 \times M$ objective functions.

To perform point association, a procedure is developed to avoid assuming the same ordering of reference points in both P'_{Xc} and P'_{Yc} clouds. The four centers in each cloud are converted to spherical coordinates, and the point with the lowest inclination angle is considered to belong to the upper row of the calibration target. The correct ordering of the remaining points is determined based on their distances to this reference point. Each point is then associated with its corresponding circle in the calibration target, namely top-left (tl), top-right (tr), bottom-left (bl), and bottom-right (br). This procedure [4] is repeated for each pose of the calibration target, and each point $\vec{p}_i$ in P'_{Xc} (and also P'_{Yc}) is labeled with $\vec{p}_{i,a}$ and $\vec{p}_{i,m}$ to denote the hole in the pattern and the corresponding pose, respectively. Additionally, a distinct color is assigned to each point, allowing for a clear visual representation of the ordering, as shown in Figure 3.5.

Subsequently, the resulting clouds P'_{Xc} and P'_{Yc} obtained from arbitrary modalities X and Y undergo a Umeyama registration procedure [41]. This procedure aims to find the rigid transformation that minimizes the distance between corresponding

Figure 3.5: Visualization of circle centers using different colors for point association

points in the clouds. The transformation matrix $\hat{T}_{XY}$ is determined by minimizing the Least-Squares Error Criterion given by:

$$\text{Least-Squares Error Criterion} = (1/4M) \sum_{i=1}^{4M} \|p_{X_i} - T_{XY}p_{Y_i}\|^2 \quad (3.2)$$

This optimization problem is solved using singular value decomposition (SVD) and provides a closed-form solution from which the set of parameters expressing the relative position between both sensors, $\hat{\theta}_{XY}$, can be straightforwardly retrieved. Conveniently, the Umeyama method handles singular situations where all the points are coplanar, as is the case when a single pattern position ($M = 1$) is used, thus avoiding misjudging them as reflections [4].

3.2 Proposed Adaptations and Enhancements for Calibration Algorithm

The *Velo2cam* Extrinsic Calibration algorithm, implemented in C++, serves as the foundation for the calibration approach. However, to ensure its versatility and applicability to various LiDAR sensors [4] under different situations, several adaptations and enhancements have been incorporated into the algorithm. These modifications aim to address specific challenges and optimize calibration accuracy. The key adaptations made to the algorithm are as follows:

3.2.1 Conversion of Unorganized Point Clouds to Range Image

To identify the circle centers on the calibration board, the unorganized point cloud must be converted into a range image. This conversion makes it possible to address the points using row and column indices, which is crucial for determining the distance to neighboring points. The conversion process involves restructuring the points into a range image with an appropriate resolution. The developer specifies the upper and lower limits of the x, y, and z coordinates of the calibration board area as program parameters using the dynamic reconfigure of ROS. This selection creates a limited-range image representing the calibration board as an organized point cloud.

3.2.2 Edge Detection on Range Image

After obtaining the range image, the next step is edge detection to filter out the edge points. There are two options available for edge detection in this context. The first option involves using the original approach described in the algorithm [4]. The second option utilizes algorithms specifically designed for range images, as mentioned in [40]. These range image-specific methods consider all surrounding points instead of just the left and right points of the target point. They employ various indicators to detect borders, such as acute impact angles or changes in normals. In this thesis, the most significant indicator, as mentioned in [40], is a change in the distance between neighboring points, which is robust against noise and changes in resolution. This feature is used to classify borders by following these steps:

1. For each image point, its local neighborhood is considered.
2. A heuristic is applied to find the typical 3D distance to neighboring points that are not across a border [40].
3. Using this information, a score is calculated to determine how likely it is that this point is part of a border [40].

To implement the edge detection process, the existing edge detection code in [4] is replaced with open-source edge detection code available in the Point Cloud Library (PCL) written in C++ [37]. Particularly, the `pcl::RangeImageBorderExtractor` from the PCL library is utilized to compute border descriptions from the range image. The points marked as obstacle borders are then extracted and stored in a new point cloud, and these points correspond to the edges detected in the range image.

Subsequently, circle detection using the RANSAC algorithm is applied to identify circles on the range image. The centers of these circles serve as the correspondent points for calibration. For each position, the correspondent points are recorded, and up to five additional positions can be recorded using the same procedure. These correspondent points form the basis for the subsequent registration step of the calibration process.

3.2.3 Implementation of Performance Metrics

In addition to the aforementioned adaptations, the implementation of performance metrics is necessary. As discussed in section 3.5, various metrics need to be calculated to evaluate the calibration algorithm's performance. This includes considering cases where ground truth is both available and unavailable, providing a comprehensive assessment of the algorithm's effectiveness.

To implement the performance metrics, code is developed to calculate the selected metrics mentioned in section 3.5. The performance evaluation takes into account various factors, such as extrinsic transformation accuracy, alignment error, and the robustness of the algorithm, employing a range of metrics. These metrics provide valuable insights and guidance for further improvements in the calibration algorithm.

3.2.4 Optimizing Calibration Accuracy: Re-Calibration

The accuracy of the calibration may face challenges under difficult data conditions, as the calibration process may include points that do not reproject equally well through the calculated transformation matrix, leading to potential inaccuracies. To address such challenges, an optimization step involving the re-calibration of the algorithm is performed after the initial calibration.

The optimization process involves filtering the source (master LiDAR) and target (slave LiDAR) point clouds based on a threshold derived from the Mean Registration Error (MRE), a performance evaluation metric further explained in detail in section 3.5. By setting the threshold at 0.15 meters, a balance is struck between having a sufficient number of points for the calibration algorithm to optimize while removing significant outliers. This filtering step eliminates points that may introduce errors in the calibration algorithm, resulting in a more robust calibration.

After filtering, the calibration algorithm is rerun using the remaining points to obtain a new transformation matrix. This optimization technique aims to improve the quality of the obtained calibration estimate. The detailed analysis of the results of this optimization technique is discussed in sections 4.2.2 and 4.3, which cover the experiments on real data and their results.

By incorporating these adaptations and enhancements, the calibration algorithm becomes more versatile and capable of handling a wider range of LiDAR sensors with unorganized point clouds, ensuring accurate and reliable calibration results.

3.3 Simulation Environment Setup

To conduct comprehensive testing and evaluation of the proposed calibration method, a simulation environment has been established using the PEV Engine (Porsche Engineering Virtual Engine). The PEV Engine (Figure 3.6) is a customized version of the

Figure 3.6: Simulation setup - CARLA simulator

CARLA simulator [6] based on the UE4 (Unreal Engine 4) engine, specifically tailored for ADAS testing. It is developed and maintained by the PEVATEC (Porsche Engineering Virtual ADAS Testing Centre) of Porsche Engineering Services.

Figure 3.7: Digital JUPITER - Porsche Cayenne E3

Within the PEV Engine, a digital representation of the JUPITER car (Figure 3.7), equipped with all the necessary sensor modalities, has been created. This digital replica enables realistic testing scenarios and data recording. Additionally, a ROS

middleware setup has been implemented to facilitate the generation and recording of sensor data.

For this thesis, a particular town and parking lot (Figure 3.8) have been selected within the simulation environment. To mimic real-world conditions, a wall and calibration board matching the required dimensions have been constructed and placed in the parking lot. This setup aims to closely resemble the physical environment, providing accurate and reliable data for the calibration process.

By utilizing the PEV Engine and creating a realistic simulation environment, controlled experiments can be conducted to evaluate the performance of the proposed calibration method under various scenarios. The simulation environment ensures reproducibility and allows for fine-tuning of the calibration parameters to achieve optimal results.

Figure 3.8: Simulation environment - Parking lot, calibration pattern placed in front of the digital JUPITER

As the simulation setup and data collection process closely mimic real-world conditions using ROS middleware, the generated data can be directly utilized with the *Velo2cam* calibration algorithm. Whether the simulation is run in real-time or based on recorded rosbags, the relevant ROS topics specific to the sensor modalities are published, and the calibration algorithm subscribes to these topics to estimate the extrinsic transformations, as mentioned by the user.

The next section, 3.4, will focus on the selection and preparation of test data in both simulation and real-world environments. These steps are crucial in the evaluation process as they enable the assessment of the proposed method's effectiveness in a simulated yet realistic setting, as well as in real-world scenarios.

3.4 Test Data Selection and Preparation

3.4.1 Calibration Board

A custom-made planar target is utilized for calibration [4], featuring characteristics that facilitate the detection and pairing of keypoints across different data representations. The calibration pattern, as shown in Figure 3.9, incorporates both geometric and visual elements that aid in estimating keypoints in LiDAR, stereo, and monocular modalities.

Figure 3.9: Calibration board containing geometric and visual features, adapted from [4]

The calibration pattern consists of four strategically positioned circular holes that exploit geometric discontinuities in LiDAR and stereo point clouds. These holes serve as distinct features that can be detected and utilized for calibration purposes. The calibration board has a height of 1000 mm and a length of 1400 mm, with circular diameters measuring 240 mm. The height difference between circle centers is 400 mm, and the length difference is 500 mm. Each circle center is positioned 300 mm in height and 450 mm in length from the nearest corner edge of the board.

Additionally, four ArUco markers [19] are placed near the corners of the calibration board. These markers enable the extraction of 3D information from monocular images. By analyzing the positions and orientations of the ArUco markers in the images, corresponding 3D points can be inferred, aiding the calibration process.

The combination of circular holes and ArUco markers on the calibration board allows for the estimation of keypoints in LiDAR, stereo, and monocular modalities, facilitating accurate and comprehensive sensor calibration.

It is important to note that although the ArUco markers are not utilized in the current thesis work, they are included on the physical calibration board. For the LiDAR sensor modality-focused research, only the circular holes are of importance. A digital replica of the calibration board, with the same dimensions, is prepared in the simulation environment to collect data from the virtual world. As expected, the digital copy does not include ArUco markers.

3.4.2 Real World Data Setup

As discussed in the Introduction (Chapter 1), the JUPITER platform incorporates various LiDAR sensors positioned in different locations around the vehicle, providing a 360-degree view of the environment. However, it is observed that some of these LiDARs do not have a significant overlapping area or may not have an overlapping area at all. Nevertheless, the *Velo2cam* calibration algorithm [4] requires an overlapping area between the sensors' FOV where the calibration target is placed [10]. To address this requirement, a new LiDAR sensor called Pandora 360 [32] is introduced on the roof of the vehicle. This Pandora 360 sensor acts as the master LiDAR and is strategically positioned to have a shared FOV overlap with each of the other LiDAR sensors individually placed on the vehicle.

3.4.2.1 Pandora 360

Pandora is an all-in-one sensing kit for autonomous driving, comprising a 40-channel LiDAR, four wide-angle monochrome cameras, and a color camera. Its all-in-one package allows for fast installation and offers a plug-and-play experience. The LiDAR sensor in Pandora has an impressive measurement range of up to 200 meters, even for objects with low reflectivity (20%), delivering a high data acquisition rate of 720,000 points per second. It achieves a vertical angular resolution of 0.33° and provides optimized laser beam distribution for enhanced detection of vehicles and pedestrians in autonomous driving scenarios.

In addition to the LiDAR sensor, Pandora includes four wide-angle monochrome cameras that provide 360° coverage around the car, along with a forward-facing color camera that captures rich visual information at a longer distance [32]. The specifications of Pandora's color camera include a resolution of 1280x720, a FOV of 52° (H), 28.6° (V), and 61° (D). Furthermore, Pandora's monochrome cameras offer a resolution of 1280x720, with a FOV of 129° (H), 81.8° (V), and 142.4° (D).

The overall specifications of the Pandora system include a height of 190 mm, a top diameter of 116 mm, and a bottom diameter of 118 mm. The rotation rate of Pandora can be set to 10 Hz or 20 Hz, and data transmission is facilitated through Ethernet with a speed of 1000 Mbps.

To utilize Pandora as a master LiDAR for calibration, it is placed on the roof of the car in such a way that it has a valid overlapping area with all the other LiDARs individually, allowing the calibration algorithm [4] to be executed.

3.4.2.2 Sensor Configuration

To set up the Pandora LiDAR, it is placed on the roof of the car and the power cord and LAN (Local area network) cable are connected to the Car-CPU. The IP address, mask, and gateway are configured according to the Pandora settings on the Car CPU. The X, Y, and Z distances are measured from the nearest ADMA GNSS2 sensor (as a reference) to obtain the initial extrinsic transformation of Pandora with respect to the base frame of the car.

3.4.2.3 Start LiDAR Sensors

All desired LiDAR sensors, including Pandora, Livox, and Blickfeld sensors, are started using the appropriate commands for the specific setup. The point clouds are verified in RVIZ to ensure that all sensors are functioning correctly and that there is a common overlapping area between Pandora and each individual sensor. The topic names of the LiDAR sensors to be calibrated, including Pandora, Livox, and Blickfeld sensors, are used for unique identification during the calibration algorithm execution.

3.4.2.4 Data Collection

Data collection for the calibration process involves recording rosbags for each direction (Front, Left, Right, and Back) using the identified sensor's topics. To ensure proper calibration, the calibration board (as mentioned above) is placed in front of the vehicle, making sure it is visible to both the Pandora and Blickfeld/Livox LiDARs' FOV.

Figure 3.10: Data collection - Calibration board held by two individuals

During the data collection process, the calibration panel was positioned perpendicular to the ground, maintaining a minimum height of 10 cm, as illustrated in Figure 3.10. To ensure consistency in positioning throughout the data collection phase, two individuals were assigned the responsibility of holding the calibration panel. However, a potential concern arises regarding the possibility of motion errors introduced by the individuals, as it is challenging to maintain complete static positions during the data capture. This may lead to the exclusion of poses where the calibration board was not stable, making them unsuitable for calibration purposes.

Figure 3.11: Real-world - Filtered point cloud, adapted from [4]

To address this limitation, a potential solution involves the development of a mechanical stand or an adjustable device that provides stability and allows for recording multiple positions of the calibration board without any movement. By employing such a stand, the need for human intervention in holding the calibration panel during data capture can be minimized, reducing the risk of introducing motion errors.

For each calibration position, a total of 30 point clouds were recorded, with each recording lasting for three seconds, and a recording frequency of 10 Hz.

To allow unique access to the recorded data, each recording is saved with a name indicating the distance between the vehicle and the pattern. This naming convention helps in organizing and referencing the data for future analysis. This data collection process is repeated for all combinations of sensors with Pandora. Considering 4 to 5 different unique positions for each combination enhances the calibration accuracy [4].

3.4.3 Simulation Data Setup

As mentioned in the section 3.3, a simulation environment has been established using the PEV Engine, a customized version of the CARLA simulator [6] based on the UE4 engine. This simulation environment (Figure 3.12) closely mimics real-world conditions and facilitates realistic testing scenarios and data recording.

Figure 3.12: Data collection setup in simulation environment

3.4.3.1 Digital JUPITER and Sensor Configuration

A digital replica of the JUPITER car, equipped with all the necessary sensor modalities, has been created within the PEV Engine. This digital representation enables accurate testing and data generation. The sensor configuration on the digital JUPITER is identical to the real JUPITER, and an additional LiDAR sensor is added on the roof to replicate the Pandora sensor [32], which acts as the master LiDAR. The ground truth of the extrinsic transformation between each individual sensor and the base frame of the car is known in the simulation environment.

3.4.3.2 LiDAR Sensor Activation

Similar to the real-world data setup, all desired LiDAR sensors, including Pandora, Livox, and Blickfeld sensors, are activated in the simulation environment. The generated point clouds are verified in RVIZ to ensure proper functionality and the existence of a common overlapping area between Pandora and each individual sensor. The topic names of the LiDAR sensors to be calibrated, including Pandora, Livox, and Blickfeld sensors, are used for unique identification during the calibration algorithm execution.

3.4.3.3 Data Collection

In the simulation environment, there is no need to record rosbags. Instead, the calibration algorithm can be executed in real-time, allowing for parameter tuning and immediate results. The detailed steps for running the calibration algorithm are explained in the next section, 3.4.4. However, it is also possible to record rosbags

Figure 3.13: Jupiter - 360-degree surround coverage LiDAR setup

in the simulation and run them at a later point in time, following the same procedure as mentioned in the section 3.4.2, to calibrate the sensors and obtain the transformations between them as results. Again, to enhance calibration accuracy, this process is repeated for 4 to 5 different unique positions for each combination of sensors with Pandora. This comprehensive approach ensures a thorough analysis and optimization of the calibration algorithm.

3.4.4 Execution of Calibration Algorithm

The execution of the calibration algorithm consists of two phases: the target segmentation phase and the Registration phase [4]. These phases play a crucial role in isolating the calibration pattern and conducting the actual calibration process. Once the data is acquired, whether in real-time simulation or from pre-recorded real-world rosbags, the calibration process can be initiated by following the steps outlined below.

3.4.4.1 Target Segmentation Phase

To initiate the calibration process, the calibration node should be launched using the appropriate launch file, specifying the point cloud topic and sensor ID. During this phase, the user must ensure that the calibration pattern is correctly represented in the data from both sensors. The procedure is carried out sequentially, one sensor

```
Creating .launch file with calibrated TF in:
/home/kaushik/carla-ros-bridge/catkin_ws/src/ros-bridge/velo2cam_calibration-master/launch/calibrated_tf.launch
Estimated Extrinsic parameters:
x = 2.4139      y = 0.0106      z = -1.0469
roll = 0.0178  pitch = -0.0916  yaw = -0.0090

Ground Truth Extrinsic parameters:
x = 2.4130      y = 0.0000      z = -1.0330
roll = 0.0000  pitch = 0.0000  yaw = 0.0000

[ INFO] [1682524334.626303285, 370.273810517]: Absolute Error t
x = 0.000892269, ty = 0.0106276, tz = 0.0139081 roll = 0.017801
7, pitch = 0.091552, yaw = 0.00896132
[ INFO] [1682524334.626355587, 370.273810517]: RMSE Total: Tran
slation = 0.0101189 Rotation = 0.0540955
[ INFO] [1682524334.626378398, 370.273810517]: MAE Total: Trans
lation = 0.00847601 Rotation = 0.0394383
[ INFO] [1682524335.000906664, 370.323810517]: Source Lidar Top
ic: /carla/ego_vehicle/pandora_frame
[ INFO] [1682524336.142995968, 370.573810521]: Similarity score
: 1.30071e-09
[ INFO] [1682524336.143778172, 370.573810521]: Point-to-point d
istance: 0.0340112
[ INFO] [1682524336.143860687, 370.573810521]: Point-to-normal
distance: 0.0172479
Calibration process finished.
Time taken by the algorithm: 30207 milliseconds
[velo2cam_calibration-1] process has finished cleanly
log file: /home/kaushik/.ros/log/b474e00e-e446-11ed-9cfb-00155d
fa36e4/velo2cam_calibration-1*.log
all processes on machine have died, roslaunch will exit
shutting down processing monitor...
... shutting down processing monitor complete
done
```

Figure 3.14: Calibration result displayed as console output

after the other, and involves two tasks. First, verifying that the pattern is within the field of view of the sensors, and second, adjusting the passthrough filters in the dynamic reconfigure to eliminate background noise and isolate the calibration pattern. Precise fine-tuning of these parameters is essential for accurately identifying the geometry of the pattern. Visual verification should be performed to ensure that the pattern's circles, edges, and centers are visible in the filtered point cloud.

3.4.4.2 Registration Phase

The registration phase begins after successfully completing the target segmentation stage separately for the two sensors that need to be calibrated and confirming that the patterns are visible in both filtered point clouds. To initiate the registration phase, the user launches the registration node using the appropriate launch file and specifies the sensor types and IDs. It is crucial to ensure that the scene remains static throughout the process, and 30 frames where the calibration pattern is correctly identified are required.

If the data is sourced from real-world rosbags, the algorithm plays the rosbag consisting of one unique position in a loop until the end of the target segmentation and registration phases. In the case of multiple recorded positions, the current rosbag is stopped, and the second rosbag with a new position is played as prompted by the algorithm at the end of the registration phase. For real-time simulation, after completing the registration phase, the algorithm prompts whether to run the target segmentation and registration phases again for a new position. At this point, the user changes the position of the calibration board in the simulation and continues the calibration process. It is recommended to repeat this procedure at least three times, each with a different position and orientation of the calibration pattern. For each iteration, the target segmentation stage is performed again with proper adjustment of the passthrough filters to accommodate the new pattern location.

Upon completion of all the poses, the algorithm displays the estimated extrinsic transformation between the two sensors as console output, as shown in Figure 3.14. The console output provides essential information about the calibration process, including the calculated transformation parameters, the performance metrics, and the time taken for the calibration. Performing calibration at multiple positions enhances the accuracy and quality of the calibration results.

3.5 Performance Metrics Selection and Justification

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the calibration algorithm, a set of carefully chosen performance metrics has been employed. These metrics aim to provide quantitative measures of the calibration algorithm's accuracy and reliability, both in scenarios with ground truth values and in real-world scenarios where ground truth values are not available. The selected metrics cover various aspects of error differences between ground truth and estimated values, as well as disparities derived from point cloud analysis.

1. **Absolute Error (AE):** The absolute error metric measures the absolute difference between the ground truth and estimated values of transformations for the sensors, including translations (x , y , z) and rotations (roll, pitch, and yaw). It provides a straightforward assessment of the calibration algorithm's ability to produce accurate results, focusing solely on the magnitude of the errors without considering their direction.

$$AE = |GT - Est| \quad (3.3)$$

Where GT represents the ground truth value, Est is the estimated value, and AE denotes the absolute error value.

2. **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** RMSE is a widely-used metric in evaluating the calibration algorithm's overall performance. It calculates the square root of the average of the squared differences between the ground truth and estimated values of transformations for the sensors. By considering both the magnitude and direction of the errors, RMSE provides a comprehensive evaluation of the algorithm's accuracy.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (GT_i - Est_i)^2} \quad (3.4)$$

Where N is the total number of samples, GT_i and Est_i are the ground truth and estimated values for the i -th sample, respectively.

3. **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** The MAE metric is another valuable measure for assessing the calibration algorithm's accuracy. It calculates the average magnitude of the absolute differences between the ground truth and estimated values of transformations for the sensors. MAE offers an effective evaluation of the calibration algorithm's accuracy while being less sensitive to outliers compared to RMSE.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |GT_i - Est_i| \quad (3.5)$$

Where N is the total number of samples, GT_i and Est_i are the ground truth and estimated values for the i -th sample, respectively.

4. **Similarity Score (SS):** The similarity score is a crucial metric for evaluating the effectiveness of a calibration algorithm in aligning two point clouds: the ground truth point cloud and the estimated point cloud obtained from the calibration process. In this context, the ground truth point cloud represents the point cloud obtained by applying the ground truth extrinsic transformations to the point cloud of the slave LiDAR, while the estimated point cloud represents the point cloud obtained by applying the extrinsic transformations obtained from the calibration process to the point cloud of the same slave LiDAR.

The similarity score evaluates how closely the estimated point cloud resembles the ground truth point cloud in terms of its structural distribution. To calculate this metric, we utilize the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) registration

technique. The similarity score is obtained by applying ICP to find the optimal transformation T_{opt} that minimizes the distance between corresponding points in P_{est} , the estimated point cloud, and P_{gt} , the ground truth point cloud. The registration is based on the following objective function:

$$T_{\text{opt}} = \arg \min_T \sum_{i=1}^N \|\vec{p}_i - T(\vec{p}'_i)\|^2 \quad (3.6)$$

where $\vec{p}_i$ is a point in P_{gt} , $\vec{p}'_i$ is the corresponding point in P_{est} , and N is the total number of corresponding points.

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) is a common metric used to measure the average squared difference between corresponding points in two point clouds. It quantifies the overall dissimilarity between the estimated point cloud and the ground truth point cloud. The MSE computes the squared Euclidean distance for each corresponding pair of points and then takes the average over all pairs. The similarity score metric is then computed as the inverse of the MSE between the estimated point cloud and the ground truth point cloud:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\vec{p}_i - \vec{p}'_i\|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{SS} = \frac{1}{1 + \text{MSE}} \quad (3.7)$$

where $\vec{p}_i$ is a point in P_{gt} , $\vec{p}'_i$ is the corresponding point in P_{est} , and N is the total number of corresponding points.

A lower similarity score indicates a more successful alignment, signifying that the calibration algorithm accurately matched the two point clouds. As a significant evaluation metric, the similarity score provides valuable insights into the algorithm's capability to capture essential features and patterns present in the ground truth point cloud.

5. **Point-to-Point (P2P) Distance:** The P2P distance metric quantifies the spatial disparities between corresponding points in the ground truth and estimated point clouds resulting from the calibration process. It provides valuable insights into the algorithm's capability to accurately align LiDAR data captured by different sensors.

For each point p_i in the estimated point cloud P_{est} and its corresponding nearest neighbor p_j in the ground truth point cloud P_{gt} , the Euclidean distance $d(p_i, p_j)$ is computed as follows:

$$d(p_i, p_j) = \sqrt{(x_{i,\text{est}} - x_{j,\text{gt}})^2 + (y_{i,\text{est}} - y_{j,\text{gt}})^2 + (z_{i,\text{est}} - z_{j,\text{gt}})^2} \quad (3.8)$$

where $(x_{i,\text{est}}, y_{i,\text{est}}, z_{i,\text{est}})$ and $(x_{j,\text{gt}}, y_{j,\text{gt}}, z_{j,\text{gt}})$ represent the Cartesian coordinates of p_i in the estimated point cloud and p_j in the ground truth point cloud, respectively.

The point-to-point distance metric is evaluated for all corresponding points in the two point clouds, and the average of all these distances gives the final P2P distance value. Smaller P2P distances indicate a more accurate alignment of spatial positions between the estimated and ground truth point clouds, reflecting the effectiveness of the calibration algorithm in minimizing systematic shifts or misalignments.

6. **Point-to-Normal (P2N) Distance:** The Point-to-Normal (P2N) distance is a metric used to assess the accuracy of the estimated surface orientations (normals) in the estimated point cloud compared to the ground truth point cloud.

For each point $\vec{p}_i$ in the estimated point cloud P_{est} , the surface normal $n_{i,\text{est}}$ is estimated using neighboring points (e.g., using normal estimation algorithms like PCA-based normal estimation). Let $n_{i,\text{gt}}$ be the corresponding surface normal in the ground truth point cloud P_{gt} . The Point-to-Normal distance $d_{\text{P2N}}(p_i)$ is calculated as the absolute difference between the estimated and ground truth normals:

$$d_{\text{P2N}}(p_i) = |n_{i,\text{est}} \cdot n_{i,\text{gt}}| \quad (3.9)$$

where $n_{i,\text{est}} \cdot n_{i,\text{gt}}$ denotes the dot product between the estimated normal $n_{i,\text{est}}$ and the ground truth normal $n_{i,\text{gt}}$.

The Point-to-Normal distance metric is evaluated for all points in the estimated point cloud, and the average of these distances gives the final P2N distance value. Smaller P2N distances indicate a better alignment of surface orientations between the estimated and ground truth point clouds, indicating the effectiveness of the calibration algorithm in accurately matching the orientation of surfaces.

Additionally, the **Mean Reprojection Error (MRE)** [15] metric has been employed to assess the algorithm's performance in real-world scenarios where ground truth values are not available. The MRE metric quantifies the differences between corresponding points in the source and target point clouds before and after the calibration process. In this context, the source point cloud refers to the point cloud of the master LiDAR, whereas the target point cloud pertains to the point cloud of the slave LiDAR.

The MRE calculation involves the following steps:

1. First, the source and target point clouds are filtered to extract the points of interest that are close to the calibration board.
2. Next, a robust algorithm (RANSAC) is applied to identify and extract points belonging to the calibration board in both point clouds.
3. Down-sampling and outlier removal techniques (e.g., Statistical Outlier Removal - SOR) are then applied to ensure the quality of the data.

Figure 3.15: Comparison of filtered LiDAR point clouds containing only calibration board before and after calibration

4. Using a nearest neighbor search algorithm (such as KD-Tree), corresponding points between the source and target point clouds are identified.
5. The MRE is computed by measuring the Euclidean distance between these corresponding points in both point clouds.

Mathematically, the MRE is given by:

$$\text{MRE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\vec{p}_i - \vec{p}'_i| \quad (3.10)$$

where N is the number of correspondences found between the target point cloud P_{est} and the source point cloud P_{gt} , and $\vec{p}_i$ and $\vec{p}'_i$ represent the corresponding points in the source and target point clouds, respectively.

Before calibration (Figure 3.15(a)), the MRE was used to analyze the initial misalignments and discrepancies between the two LiDAR sources, establishing a baseline for comparison. After calibration (Figure 3.15(b)), the MRE was recalculated to assess the disparities between the source and target point clouds once again. Comparing the MRE values before and after calibration allowed for an evaluation of the algorithm's effectiveness in reducing disparities and improving alignment between the LiDAR point clouds.

By employing this comprehensive set of performance metrics, the developed calibration algorithm can be rigorously evaluated, providing valuable insights into its accuracy, reliability, and ability to pre-calibrate LiDAR sensors based on a simulation environment.

4 Experimental Evaluation

To validate and assess the performance of the developed calibration algorithm for LiDAR sensors, a comprehensive study was conducted in both a simulation environment and real-world scenarios. This experimental evaluation helped in investigating the impact of various parameter settings on the calibration output and provided valuable insights into the algorithm’s behavior and robustness.

4.1 Simulation Experiments

The simulation experiments were designed to mimic real-world scenarios and involved generating synthetic point clouds with known ground truth values. By systematically varying the parameters such as the number of calibration positions, relative distances, and noise levels, the algorithm’s sensitivity and accuracy were evaluated. The selected performance metrics, including absolute error, RMSE, MAE, similarity score, point-to-point difference, and point-to-normal difference, were calculated to quantitatively assess the calibration algorithm’s performance.

The simulation experiments yielded valuable insights into the algorithm’s performance and formed the basis for comparing its effectiveness in subsequent real-world experiments. For clarity, all tables presented in this section utilize meters and degrees as units for translation values (x , y , z , Translation, P2P) and rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation), respectively. Additionally, SS and P2N values are dimensionless.

4.1.1 Translation of the Sensor

To assess the impact of relative sensor translation distance on calibration accuracy, various values of translation along the x , y , and z axes were examined. This revealed the relationship between sensor displacement and calibration error, offering valuable insights for pre-calibration procedures.

The experimental results, including both the ground truth values and their corresponding estimated values, along with the metrics used for quantitative assessment of calibration performance, are presented in the following tables. These tables provide a comprehensive evaluation of the calibration algorithm’s performance.

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: 0.0122 z: -1.0499 roll: 1.2724 pitch: -0.1318 yaw: -0.0224	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0122 z: 0.0169 roll: 1.2724 pitch: 0.1318 yaw: 0.0224	Translation: 0.0121 Rotation: 0.7387	Translation: 0.0102 Rotation: 0.4755	4.3262e-10	0.3388	0.1602
x: 2.6130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.6149 y: 0.0173 z: -1.0450 roll: 1.2835 pitch: -0.1582 yaw: 0.0073	x: 0.0019 y: 0.0173 z: 0.0120 roll: 1.2835 pitch: 0.1582 yaw: 0.0073	Translation: 0.0122 Rotation: 0.7466	Translation: 0.0104 Rotation: 0.4830	1.6515e-09	0.3452	0.1655
x: 2.8130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.8147 y: -0.0031 z: -1.0445 roll: -0.0102 pitch: -0.1610 yaw: 0.0120	x: 0.0017 y: 0.0031 z: 0.0115 roll: 0.0102 pitch: 0.1610 yaw: 0.0120	Translation: 0.0069 Rotation: 0.0934	Translation: 0.0054 Rotation: 0.0611	1.6293e-09	0.0486	0.0243
x: 3.0130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 3.0147 y: -0.0001 z: -1.0434 roll: 0.1920 pitch: -0.1377 yaw: -0.0013	x: 0.0017 y: 0.0001 z: 0.0104 roll: 0.1920 pitch: 0.1377 yaw: 0.0013	Translation: 0.0061 Rotation: 0.1364	Translation: 0.0041 Rotation: 0.1103	4.7179e-09	0.0642	0.0310
x: 3.2130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 3.2131 y: -0.0013 z: -1.0363 roll: 0.0477 pitch: -0.0132 yaw: -0.0055	x: 0.0001 y: 0.0013 z: 0.0033 roll: 0.0477 pitch: 0.0132 yaw: 0.0055	Translation: 0.0020 Rotation: 0.0288	Translation: 0.0016 Rotation: 0.0221	3.4813e-10	0.0139	0.0070
x: 3.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 3.4150 y: -0.0047 z: -1.0452 roll: 0.0788 pitch: -0.1574 yaw: 0.0124	x: 0.0020 y: 0.0047 z: 0.0122 roll: 0.0788 pitch: 0.1574 yaw: 0.0124	Translation: 0.0076 Rotation: 0.1019	Translation: 0.0063 Rotation: 0.0829	1.6600e-10	0.0517	0.0258
x: 3.6130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 3.6145 y: 0.0047 z: -1.0415 roll: 0.9104 pitch: -0.1281 yaw: -0.0110	x: 0.0015 y: 0.0047 z: 0.0085 roll: 0.9104 pitch: 0.1281 yaw: 0.0110	Translation: 0.0057 Rotation: 0.5308	Translation: 0.0049 Rotation: 0.3498	1.5791e-09	0.2468	0.1182
x: 3.8130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 3.8145 y: 0.0068 z: -1.0486 roll: 0.9183 pitch: -0.1360 yaw: -0.0109	x: 0.0015 y: 0.0068 z: 0.0156 roll: 0.9183 pitch: 0.1360 yaw: 0.0109	Translation: 0.0099 Rotation: 0.5360	Translation: 0.0080 Rotation: 0.3551	9.7738e-11	0.2501	0.1215
x: 4.0130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 4.0144 y: -0.0060 z: -1.0593 roll: -0.3999 pitch: -0.1727 yaw: 0.0267	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0060 z: 0.0263 roll: 0.3999 pitch: 0.1727 yaw: 0.0267	Translation: 0.0156 Rotation: 0.2519	Translation: 0.0112 Rotation: 0.1998	1.5730e-09	0.1173	0.0577

Table 4.1: Effect of relative sensor translation in X direction on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

- **X distance:** The X distance was systematically varied from 2.4 meters to 4.0 meters in increments of 0.2 meters. The impact of this variation on the calibration results is presented in Table 4.1. The calibration process showed remarkable consistency across this range of X values. The analysis, as de-

picted in Figure 4.1, indicates consistently low AE values in the X direction, particularly when the relative sensor translation in the X direction falls within the 3 to 3.2 meters range. The RMSE and MAE values in both translation and rotation also remained relatively small, especially within this optimal 3 to 3.2 meters range, suggesting effective control of calibration errors in the translation components.

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: -0.4000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4147 y: -0.4071 z: -1.0357 roll: 0.1251 pitch: -0.1338 yaw: 0.0136	x: 0.0017 y: 0.0071 z: 0.0027 roll: 0.1251 pitch: 0.1338 yaw: 0.0136	Translation: 0.0045 Rotation: 0.1060	Translation: 0.0038 Rotation: 0.0908	5.0259e-11	0.0514	0.0250
x: 2.4130 y: -0.2000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4140 y: -0.2326 z: -1.0419 roll: -1.0951 pitch: -0.1196 yaw: 0.0813	x: 0.0010 y: 0.0326 z: 0.0089 roll: 1.0951 pitch: 0.1196 yaw: 0.0813	Translation: 0.0195 Rotation: 0.6377	Translation: 0.0142 Rotation: 0.4320	4.4032e-10	0.3027	0.1440
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4133 y: 0.0065 z: -1.0358 roll: 0.4961 pitch: -0.0349 yaw: -0.0361	x: 0.0003 y: 0.0065 z: 0.0028 roll: 0.4961 pitch: 0.0349 yaw: 0.0361	Translation: 0.0041 Rotation: 0.2879	Translation: 0.0032 Rotation: 0.1890	1.9324e-10	0.1349	0.0642
x: 2.4130 y: 0.2000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4139 y: 0.1986 z: -1.0397 roll: 0.2453 pitch: -0.1253 yaw: -0.0177	x: 0.0009 y: 0.0014 z: 0.0067 roll: 0.2453 pitch: 0.1253 yaw: 0.0177	Translation: 0.0040 Rotation: 0.1593	Translation: 0.0030 Rotation: 0.1294	1.0257e-09	0.0745	0.0357
x: 2.4130 y: 0.4000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4143 y: 0.4093 z: -1.0459 roll: 0.8454 pitch: -0.1276 yaw: -0.0008	x: 0.0013 y: 0.0093 z: 0.0129 roll: 0.8454 pitch: 0.1276 yaw: 0.0008	Translation: 0.0092 Rotation: 0.4936	Translation: 0.0078 Rotation: 0.3246	5.4713e-10	0.2293	0.1068

Table 4.2: Effect of relative sensor translation in Y direction on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

Additionally, the analysis of the table 4.1 reveals that the SS, P2P, and P2N values exhibited minor fluctuations but remained relatively small. Overall, the effect of relative sensor translation in the X direction on calibration indicates excellent calibration performance, with the 3 to 3.2 meters range standing out as an optimal region. This information is crucial for optimizing the calibration process, especially when dealing with real-world data within this specific X-distance range.

- **Y distance:** Similarly, the Y distance was varied from -0.4 to 0.4 meters with an increment of 0.2 meters. The results are summarized in table 4.2. Similar to the X distance, the Y distance had no significant effect on calibration accuracy within this selected range. The AE in the Y direction remained consistently low as shown in 4.2, indicating a precise estimation of extrinsic parameters

Figure 4.1: Effect of relative sensor translation in X direction on calibration

during calibration. Both RMSE and MAE values for translation and rotation were consistently small, demonstrating accurate estimation of positional and rotational changes.

Despite minor spikes that could be attributed to noise or data quality issues, the calibration process exhibited excellent performance and consistency. The small variations in SS, P2P, and P2N values further confirmed the calibration’s accuracy. These results instill confidence in the reliability of the calibration process for various applications, even when dealing with different Y-distance variations.

Figure 4.2: Effect of relative sensor translation in Y direction on calibration

- Z distance:** Similar to the previous experiments, the calibration process was evaluated with varying relative sensor translations in the Z direction. The Z distance between the sensors varied from -1.0 to -1.5 meters with an increment of 0.1 meters. The calibration results are presented in Table 4.3.

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4132 y: 0.0010 z: -1.0320 roll: 0.2849 pitch: -0.0396 yaw: 0.0025	x: 0.0002 y: 0.0010 z: 0.0010 roll: 0.2849 pitch: 0.0396 yaw: 0.0025	Translation: 0.0008 Rotation: 0.1661	Translation: 0.0007 Rotation: 0.1090	9.5954e-10	0.0766	0.0367
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.1330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4154 y: 0.0152 z: -1.1495 roll: 1.4207 pitch: -0.1735 yaw: 0.0068	x: 0.0024 y: 0.0152 z: 0.0165 roll: 1.4207 pitch: 0.1735 yaw: 0.0068	Translation: 0.0130 Rotation: 0.8263	Translation: 0.0114 Rotation: 0.5337	1.0088e-09	0.3888	0.1871
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.2330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4146 y: 0.0123 z: -1.2369 roll: 1.2053 pitch: -0.1048 yaw: -0.0388	x: 0.0016 y: 0.0123 z: 0.0039 roll: 1.2053 pitch: 0.1048 yaw: 0.0388	Translation: 0.0075 Rotation: 0.6989	Translation: 0.0059 Rotation: 0.4496	7.8402e-10	0.3411	0.1637
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.3330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: -0.0127 z: -1.3248 roll: -0.0489 pitch: -0.0789 yaw: 0.0157	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0127 z: 0.0082 roll: 0.0489 pitch: 0.0789 yaw: 0.0157	Translation: 0.0088 Rotation: 0.0544	Translation: 0.0074 Rotation: 0.0478	1.8054e-10	0.0335	0.0157
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.4330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: -0.0061 z: -1.4377 roll: 0.1456 pitch: -0.0563 yaw: 0.0391	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0061 z: 0.0047 roll: 0.1456 pitch: 0.0563 yaw: 0.0391	Translation: 0.0045 Rotation: 0.0929	Translation: 0.0041 Rotation: 0.0803	5.3985e-10	0.0510	0.0250
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.5330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4152 y: 0.0094 z: -1.5121 roll: 1.5205 pitch: -0.0865 yaw: -0.0197	x: 0.0022 y: 0.0094 z: 0.0209 roll: 1.5205 pitch: 0.0865 yaw: 0.0197	Translation: 0.0133 Rotation: 0.8794	Translation: 0.0108 Rotation: 0.5422	1.3642e-09	0.4599	0.2194

Table 4.3: Effect of relative sensor translation in Z direction on the calibration (all translation relative values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

As observed in the previous cases, the changes in Z distance did not have a significant impact on the RMSE and MAE values for both translation and rotation. The calibration algorithm demonstrated consistent and accurate performance across the range of Z distances.

The plot in Figure 4.3 illustrates the calibration errors with respect to the ground truth Z values. It reveals that as the ground truth Z value deviates from zero, the AE in Z increases, indicating reduced accuracy in estimating sensor positions along the Z-axis with larger Z translations. Despite this, the AE values remain relatively small, implying reasonable accuracy for different Z translations.

However, it is important to note that as the Z distance between sensors increased, the FOV overlap area between the sensor point clouds decreased. This decrease in the possible area for the placement of the calibration board can make the calibration process more challenging. A reduced FOV overlap may

result in fewer correspondences between the point clouds from the sensors, potentially leading to less precise calibration estimations.

Therefore, while the calibration algorithm remains robust to changes in sensor z distance, careful consideration should be given to selecting an appropriate Z distance that ensures an adequate FOV overlap for accurate calibration. The findings from this experiment provide valuable insights for optimizing the calibration setup and improving its performance, especially when dealing with large Z distance variations between sensors.

Figure 4.3: Effect of relative sensor translation in Z direction on calibration

4.1.2 Rotation of the Sensor

Similar to the translation experiments, the calibration performance was examined by varying the rotational angles between sensors. Rotations were applied around the roll, pitch, and yaw axes. The findings shed light on the calibration method’s sensitivity to sensor rotation, providing valuable information for understanding and optimizing the calibration process.

- Roll:** The calibration process involved evaluating various relative roll angles between -20 and 20 degrees, with a 5 -degree increment. For roll angles between -5 and 5 degrees, a finer increment of 2.5 degrees was used. Table 4.4 summarizes the calibration results under different roll angle configurations. Notably, the calibration method demonstrated robustness to changes in the roll angle, with RMSE and MAE values exhibiting minimal fluctuations. This consistency indicates accurate calibration performance across the range of roll values.

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: -20.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4145 y: -0.3474 z: -0.9905 roll: -19.3681 pitch: -0.1110 yaw: 0.0444	x: 0.0015 y: 0.3474 z: 0.0425 roll: 0.6319 pitch: 0.1110 yaw: 0.0444	Translation: 0.2021 Rotation: 0.3713	Translation: 0.1305 Rotation: 0.2624	2.3934e-10	0.3685	0.1894
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: -15.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4145 y: -0.2611 z: -1.0140 roll: -14.0816 pitch: -0.1295 yaw: -0.0057	x: 0.0015 y: 0.2611 z: 0.0190 roll: 0.9184 pitch: 0.1295 yaw: 0.0057	Translation: 0.1511 Rotation: 0.5355	Translation: 0.0939 Rotation: 0.3512	6.4088e-10	0.3355	0.1694
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: -10.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4141 y: -0.1639 z: -1.0305 roll: -8.8908 pitch: -0.1140 yaw: -0.0239	x: 0.0011 y: 0.1639 z: 0.0025 roll: 1.1092 pitch: 0.1140 yaw: 0.0239	Translation: 0.0946 Rotation: 0.6439	Translation: 0.0558 Rotation: 0.4157	8.7025e-10	0.3075	0.1628
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: -5.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4139 y: -0.0838 z: -1.0357 roll: -4.8553 pitch: -0.1123 yaw: 0.0103	x: 0.0008 y: 0.0838 z: 0.0027 roll: 0.1447 pitch: 0.1123 yaw: 0.0103	Translation: 0.0484 Rotation: 0.1059	Translation: 0.0291 Rotation: 0.0891	3.0163e-10	0.1020	0.0435
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: -2.5000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4147 y: -0.0338 z: -1.0452 roll: -1.9346 pitch: -0.1429 yaw: 0.0154	x: 0.0017 y: 0.0338 z: 0.0122 roll: 0.5654 pitch: 0.1429 yaw: 0.0154	Translation: 0.0208 Rotation: 0.3368	Translation: 0.0159 Rotation: 0.2412	7.9765e-10	0.1568	0.0800
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0036 z: -1.0384 roll: 0.3785 pitch: -0.0340 yaw: -0.0109	x: 0.0000 y: 0.0036 z: 0.0054 roll: 0.3785 pitch: 0.0340 yaw: 0.0109	Translation: 0.0037 Rotation: 0.2195	Translation: 0.0030 Rotation: 0.1411	3.4427e-11	0.1016	0.0483
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 2.5000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4146 y: 0.0590 z: -1.0380 roll: 3.7697 pitch: -0.1282 yaw: -0.0192	x: 0.0016 y: 0.0590 z: 0.0050 roll: 1.2697 pitch: 0.1282 yaw: 0.0192	Translation: 0.0342 Rotation: 0.7369	Translation: 0.0219 Rotation: 0.4724	4.6952e-10	0.3567	0.1699
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 5.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4145 y: 0.0934 z: -1.0331 roll: 5.8511 pitch: -0.1245 yaw: -0.0283	x: 0.0015 y: 0.0934 z: 0.0001 roll: 0.8511 pitch: 0.1245 yaw: 0.0283	Translation: 0.0539 Rotation: 0.4969	Translation: 0.0317 Rotation: 0.3346	1.5089e-09	0.2627	0.1200
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 10.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: 0.1996 z: -1.0320 roll: 12.8875 pitch: -0.1039 yaw: -0.0463	x: 0.0014 y: 0.1996 z: 0.0010 roll: 2.8875 pitch: 0.1039 yaw: 0.0463	Translation: 0.1152 Rotation: 1.6684	Translation: 0.0673 Rotation: 1.0126	3.8121e-10	0.7795	0.3654
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 15.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4152 y: 0.2686 z: -1.0207 roll: 14.7860 pitch: -0.1731 yaw: -0.0417	x: 0.0022 y: 0.2686 z: 0.0123 roll: 0.2139 pitch: 0.1731 yaw: 0.0417	Translation: 0.1552 Rotation: 0.1607	Translation: 0.0944 Rotation: 0.1429	1.1072e-09	0.2792	0.1331
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 20.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4143 y: 0.3639 z: -0.9817 roll: 21.0740 pitch: -0.1233 yaw: -0.0263	x: 0.0013 y: 0.3639 z: 0.0513 roll: 1.0740 pitch: 0.1233 yaw: 0.0263	Translation: 0.2122 Rotation: 0.6243	Translation: 0.1388 Rotation: 0.4079	1.472e-09	0.4979	0.1707

Table 4.4: Effect of relative sensor rotation (roll) on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

Figure 4.4: Effect of relative sensor rotation (roll) on calibration

Figure 4.4 visually presents the calibration results concerning the roll angles. It illustrates that the AE in roll remains relatively low, particularly at small ground truth roll angles. However, as the ground truth roll angle deviates from zero, the AE increases, suggesting a decrease in calibration accuracy at larger roll angles. Nonetheless, the calibration algorithm still provides reasonable estimations even at higher roll angles.

Additionally, the plot depicts the RMSE in translation and rotation, as well as the MAE in translation and rotation. These error metrics display consistent behavior, with increased stability observed when the ground truth roll angle difference is close to zero. This stability signifies reliable calibration performance in the vicinity of zero roll angles.

In conclusion, the calibration method exhibits robustness to variations in sensor roll orientation, delivering consistent and accurate calibration results. The highest accuracy is achieved when the relative roll differences between sensors are near zero.

Figure 4.5: Effect of relative sensor rotation (pitch) on calibration

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: -8.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.5355 y: -0.0083 z: -0.6916 roll: 0.2960 pitch: -8.1137 yaw: 0.0362	x: 0.1225 y: 0.0083 z: 0.3414 roll: 0.2960 pitch: 0.1137 yaw: 0.0362	Translation: 0.2095 Rotation: 0.1842	Translation: 0.1574 Rotation: 0.1486	2.9548e-10	0.3664	0.2237
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: -6.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.5094 y: -0.0014 z: -0.7816 roll: 0.1464 pitch: -6.0654 yaw: 0.0267	x: 0.0964 y: 0.0014 z: 0.2514 roll: 0.1464 pitch: 0.0654 yaw: 0.0267	Translation: 0.1555 Rotation: 0.0938	Translation: 0.1164 Rotation: 0.0795	1.1514e-09	0.2692	0.1671
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: -4.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4787 y: 0.0110 z: -0.8645 roll: 1.2190 pitch: -3.9642 yaw: -0.0123	x: 0.0657 y: 0.0110 z: 0.1685 roll: 1.2190 pitch: 0.0358 yaw: 0.0123	Translation: 0.1046 Rotation: 0.7041	Translation: 0.0817 Rotation: 0.4224	3.3981e-09	0.3716	0.1966
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: -2.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4480 y: 0.0091 z: -0.9420 roll: 0.5841 pitch: -2.0636 yaw: 0.0017	x: 0.0350 y: 0.0091 z: 0.0910 roll: 0.5841 pitch: 0.0636 yaw: 0.0017	Translation: 0.0565 Rotation: 0.3392	Translation: 0.0450 Rotation: 0.2165	4.4386e-10	0.1869	0.0956
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4130 y: -0.0019 z: -1.0363 roll: -0.0124 pitch: -0.0079 yaw: 0.0053	x: 0.0000 y: 0.0019 z: 0.0033 roll: 0.0124 pitch: 0.0079 yaw: 0.0053	Translation: 0.0022 Rotation: 0.0090	Translation: 0.0017 Rotation: 0.0085	6.8460e-11	0.0061	0.0033
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 2.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.3767 y: 0.0021 z: -1.1291 roll: 0.7608 pitch: 1.8712 yaw: 0.0310	x: 0.0363 y: 0.0021 z: 0.0961 roll: 0.7608 pitch: 0.1288 yaw: 0.0310	Translation: 0.0593 Rotation: 0.4459	Translation: 0.0448 Rotation: 0.3069	7.7133e-10	0.2322	0.1173
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 4.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.3373 y: 0.0113 z: -1.2008 roll: 1.5260 pitch: 3.8360 yaw: -0.0116	x: 0.0757 y: 0.0113 z: 0.1678 roll: 1.5260 pitch: 0.1640 yaw: 0.0116	Translation: 0.1065 Rotation: 0.8861	Translation: 0.0849 Rotation: 0.5672	1.8234e-09	0.4476	0.2195

Table 4.5: Effect of relative sensor rotation (pitch) on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

- **Pitch:** The pitch angle was varied from -8 to 4 degrees with a 2-degree increment. Similar to the roll experiments, the calibration method exhibited robustness to changes in the pitch angle. The AE, RMSE, and MAE values remained relatively low and close to zero, particularly at zero pitch angle difference between the sensors. This indicates successful convergence to the minimum error for both translation and rotation estimations at this specific pitch angle configuration as shown in Figure 4.5. The calibration algorithm’s stability and accuracy were evident, as the calibration results exhibited minimal fluctuations. This robustness underscores the calibration method’s reliability and effectiveness, making it suitable for various sensor setups and applications.

Experimental Evaluation

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: -8.0000	x: 2.3917 y: -0.3284 z: -1.0521 roll: -0.9524 pitch: -0.1245 yaw: -7.9113	x: 0.0213 y: 0.3284 z: 0.0191 roll: 0.9524 pitch: 0.1245 yaw: 0.0887	Translation: 0.1903 Rotation: 0.5569	Translation: 0.1229 Rotation: 0.3885	8.3042e-10	0.4594	0.1681
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: -6.0000	x: 2.3974 y: -0.2772 z: -1.0431 roll: 0.9182 pitch: -0.1244 yaw: -5.9570	x: 0.0156 y: 0.2772 z: 0.0101 roll: 0.9182 pitch: 0.1244 yaw: 0.0430	Translation: 0.1604 Rotation: 0.5355	Translation: 0.1010 Rotation: 0.3619	1.3330e-09	0.3959	0.1788
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: -4.0000	x: 2.4077 y: -0.1760 z: -1.0461 roll: -0.5903 pitch: -0.1261 yaw: -3.9666	x: 0.0053 y: 0.1760 z: 0.0131 roll: 0.5903 pitch: 0.1261 yaw: 0.0334	Translation: 0.1020 Rotation: 0.3490	Translation: 0.0648 Rotation: 0.2499	5.7619e-10	0.2629	0.0983
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: -2.0000	x: 2.4114 y: -0.0936 z: -1.0405 roll: 0.5765 pitch: -0.1252 yaw: -2.0284	x: 0.0016 y: 0.0936 z: 0.0075 roll: 0.5765 pitch: 0.1252 yaw: 0.0284	Translation: 0.0542 Rotation: 0.3410	Translation: 0.0342 Rotation: 0.2434	3.2279e-11	0.1913	0.0944
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4132 y: 0.0089 z: -1.0339 roll: 0.9368 pitch: -0.0342 yaw: -0.0155	x: 0.0002 y: 0.0089 z: 0.0009 roll: 0.9368 pitch: 0.0342 yaw: 0.0155	Translation: 0.0052 Rotation: 0.5413	Translation: 0.0033 Rotation: 0.3288	1.7963e-10	0.2482	0.1157
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 2.0000	x: 2.4119 y: 0.0947 z: -1.0637 roll: 1.2319 pitch: -0.1227 yaw: 1.9754	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0947 z: 0.0307 roll: 1.2319 pitch: 0.1227 yaw: 0.0246	Translation: 0.0575 Rotation: 0.7149	Translation: 0.0422 Rotation: 0.4597	1.3439e-09	0.3663	0.1629
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 4.0000	x: 2.4083 y: 0.1690 z: -1.0438 roll: 1.0421 pitch: -0.1307 yaw: 3.9599	x: 0.0047 y: 0.1690 z: 0.0108 roll: 1.0421 pitch: 0.1307 yaw: 0.0401	Translation: 0.0978 Rotation: 0.6068	Translation: 0.0615 Rotation: 0.4043	5.9153e-10	0.3626	0.1503
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 6.0000	x: 2.4020 y: 0.2291 z: -1.0484 roll: -0.2095 pitch: -0.0564 yaw: 5.9575	x: 0.0110 y: 0.2291 z: 0.0154 roll: 0.2095 pitch: 0.0564 yaw: 0.0425	Translation: 0.1327 Rotation: 0.1276	Translation: 0.0852 Rotation: 0.1028	1.1231e-09	0.2422	0.0873
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 8.0000	x: 2.3891 y: 0.3469 z: -1.0408 roll: 1.0575 pitch: -0.1267 yaw: 7.9384	x: 0.0239 y: 0.3469 z: 0.0078 roll: 1.0575 pitch: 0.1267 yaw: 0.0616	Translation: 0.2008 Rotation: 0.6159	Translation: 0.1262 Rotation: 0.4153	1.1599e-09	0.5015	0.1849

Table 4.6: Effect of relative sensor rotation (yaw) on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

- **Yaw:** The yaw angle was varied from -8 to 8 degrees with a 2-degree increment. Similar results were observed. The results are summarized in table 4.6. The AE in yaw remains relatively low for most ground truth yaw angles, with a

slight increase observed as the ground truth yaw angle deviates from zero, as shown in Figure 4.6. This highlights the calibration algorithm’s sensitivity to larger yaw angles and emphasizes the importance of accurate yaw estimation during calibration. Regarding translation and rotation, the RMSE and MAE values demonstrate consistent behavior across yaw angles, indicating stable and reliable calibration performance even with changes in yaw orientation.

In conclusion, the calibration algorithm presented in this study offers reliable and robust calibration performance, making it a valuable tool for calibrating sensors with varying rotation angles. However, in all these rotation cases, it is crucial to ensure the existence of a FOV overlap area where it is possible to place a calibration board.

Figure 4.6: Effect of relative sensor rotation (yaw) on calibration

4.1.3 Impact of Number of Poses

To analyze the influence of the number of poses on calibration accuracy, a comparative study was conducted to assess how single-pose and multi-pose configurations affect calibration results. The objective was to understand the significance of considering multiple poses for achieving robust pre-calibration.

By varying the sensor poses while maintaining coplanarity, valuable insights were gained regarding the calibration algorithm’s performance. The calibration accuracy was evaluated and compared using RMSE and MAE values. Table 4.7 provides a summary of the results, revealing a clear trend: as the number of poses increased, the calibration accuracy improved.

Figure 4.7 visually demonstrates the calibration results, reinforcing the observation that RMSE in translation decreases with an increasing number of poses, indicating enhanced accuracy in estimating the translational components. Conversely, RMSE in rotation remains relatively stable, showing only a slight decrease as the number of poses increases. This suggests that the rotational components are already accurately estimated, and additional poses have a relatively smaller impact on their

Figure 4.7: RMSE and MAE in translation and rotation vs. number of poses

improvement compared to translation. Similarly, the MAE in translation and rotation also demonstrate a decreasing trend, signifying improved accuracy in estimating translational and rotational components with an increasing number of poses.

For example, the translation error across the three axes decreased from 0.0081 meters in the single-pose configuration to 0.0008 meters in the five co-planar poses. Likewise, for rotation, the error reduced from 0.7101 degrees in the single-pose configuration to 0.1746 degrees in the five co-planar poses. These findings emphasize that incorporating more poses during calibration leads to enhanced accuracy in the calibration process.

Poses	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
Single pose	x: 2.4144 y: 0.0086 z: -1.0440 roll: 1.2232 pitch: -0.1293 yaw: -0.0078	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0086 z: 0.0094 roll: 1.2232 pitch: 0.1293 yaw: 0.0078	Translation: 0.0081 Rotation: 0.7101	Translation: 0.0070 Rotation: 0.4534	2.1002e-07	0.3283	0.1570
Three co-planar poses	x: 2.4141 y: 0.0020 z: -1.0365 roll: 0.1847 pitch: 0.0575 yaw: 0.0056	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0020 z: 0.0035 roll: 0.1847 pitch: 0.0575 yaw: 0.0056	Translation: 0.0024 Rotation: 0.1117	Translation: 0.0022 Rotation: 0.0826	4.8837e-07	0.0520	0.0244
Five co-planar poses	x: 2.4141 y: 0.0009 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.2848 pitch: -0.1017 yaw: 0.0035	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0009 z: 0.0000 roll: 0.2848 pitch: 0.1017 yaw: 0.0035	Translation: 0.0008 Rotation: 0.1746	Translation: 0.0007 Rotation: 0.1300	4.0483e-07	0.0809	0.0378

Table 4.7: Effect of number of unique sensor positions on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

The comparison between single-pose and multi-pose configurations clearly highlights the significance of utilizing multiple poses during calibration to achieve robust and accurate results. Additional poses enable the calibration algorithm to effectively

compensate for noise, uncertainties, and limited overlapping Field of View (FOV) areas, resulting in improved calibration accuracy. As a result, it is recommended to employ multiple co-planar poses during sensor system calibration to enhance overall accuracy and reliability.

4.1.4 Stability on Repetitions (Randomness)

The calibration method's stability and reliability were extensively investigated by conducting multiple repetitions of the calibration process using the same parameters. This examination aimed to assess the calibration method's consistency and repeatability in the face of inherent randomness, shedding light on its robustness.

The analysis of the calibration results, as presented in Table 4.8, reveals remarkable consistency. Despite the incorporation of randomization in various algorithmic steps, such as plane segmentation, circle segmentation, and outlier filtering, the calibration outputs show minimal sensitivity to randomness. To further understand the impact of randomness, the standard deviation of absolute errors for both translation and rotation parameters was computed. These standard deviations provide a quantitative measure of the calibration method's stability against random fluctuations. The results are depicted in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Standard deviation of absolute errors for translation and rotation parameters determining the consistency of the calibration results against random components in the algorithm

From the graph, it is evident that the standard deviations for the translation parameters (x, y, z) are small, indicating consistent and accurate estimation of the translational components. Similarly, though the standard deviations for the rotation parameters (roll, pitch, yaw) are slightly higher, they are still reasonably small, further supporting the method's reliability in estimating the rotational components. Particularly, the y, z, and roll parameters exhibit relatively higher standard deviations, indicating increased sensitivity to random fluctuations introduced during the calibration process.

Experimental Evaluation

Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4143 y: 0.0024 z: -1.0422 roll: 0.5072 pitch: -0.1140 yaw: 0.0070	x: 0.0013 y: 0.0024 z: 0.0092 roll: 0.5072 pitch: 0.1140 yaw: 0.0070	Translation: 0.0055 Rotation: 0.3002	Translation: 0.0043 Rotation: 0.2094	7.9618e-10	0.1383	0.0662
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4143 y: 0.0043 z: -1.0499 roll: 0.5682 pitch: -0.1286 yaw: 0.0051	x: 0.0013 y: 0.0043 z: 0.0169 roll: 0.5682 pitch: 0.1286 yaw: 0.0051	Translation: 0.0101 Rotation: 0.3364	Translation: 0.0075 Rotation: 0.2340	1.8357e-09	0.1570	0.0734
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4140 y: 0.0049 z: -1.0534 roll: 0.1870 pitch: -0.0935 yaw: 0.0022	x: 0.0010 y: 0.0049 z: 0.0204 roll: 0.1870 pitch: 0.0935 yaw: 0.0022	Translation: 0.0121 Rotation: 0.1207	Translation: 0.0088 Rotation: 0.0942	2.1708e-11	0.0598	0.0290
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4140 y: -0.0018 z: -1.0532 roll: -0.6613 pitch: -0.0929 yaw: 0.0252	x: 0.0010 y: 0.0018 z: 0.0202 roll: 0.6613 pitch: 0.0929 yaw: 0.0252	Translation: 0.0117 Rotation: 0.3858	Translation: 0.0077 Rotation: 0.2598	3.6875e-10	0.1766	0.0853
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4141 y: -0.0049 z: -1.0501 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0049 z: 0.0171 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	Translation: 0.0103 Rotation: 0.6285	Translation: 0.0077 Rotation: 0.4039	1.908e-09	0.2862	0.1354
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4142 y: 0.0088 z: -1.0408 roll: 0.3629 pitch: -0.0954 yaw: -0.0017	x: 0.0012 y: 0.0088 z: 0.0078 roll: 0.3629 pitch: 0.0954 yaw: 0.0017	Translation: 0.0068 Rotation: 0.2166	Translation: 0.0059 Rotation: 0.1533	2.5303e-09	0.1025	0.0483
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4141 y: -0.0032 z: -1.0271 roll: -1.4644 pitch: -0.0844 yaw: 0.0162	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0032 z: 0.0059 roll: 1.4644 pitch: 0.0844 yaw: 0.0162	Translation: 0.0039 Rotation: 0.8469	Translation: 0.0034 Rotation: 0.5217	3.7487e-10	0.3815	0.1847
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4138 y: 0.0179 z: -1.0443 roll: 1.1528 pitch: -0.0772 yaw: -0.0565	x: 0.0008 y: 0.0179 z: 0.0113 roll: 1.1528 pitch: 0.0772 yaw: 0.0565	Translation: 0.0122 Rotation: 0.6679	Translation: 0.01 Rotation: 0.4288	2.9742e-10	0.3087	0.1475
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4139 y: 0.0129 z: -1.0344 roll: 0.4387 pitch: -0.0712 yaw: -0.0325	x: 0.0009 y: 0.0129 z: 0.0014 roll: 0.4387 pitch: 0.0712 yaw: 0.0325	Translation: 0.0075 Rotation: 0.2573	Translation: 0.0051 Rotation: 0.1808	2.5435e-10	0.1229	0.0578
x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4137 y: 0.0142 z: -1.0381 roll: 0.5317 pitch: -0.0686 yaw: -0.0418	x: 0.0007 y: 0.0142 z: 0.0051 roll: 0.5317 pitch: 0.0686 yaw: 0.0418	Translation: 0.0087 Rotation: 0.3105	Translation: 0.0067 Rotation: 0.2140	1.1898e-09	0.1482	0.0688

Table 4.8: Effect of randomness on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

In conclusion, the analysis demonstrates that the calibration method performs exceptionally well in the presence of randomness, offering consistent and reliable results across multiple repetitions. The low standard deviations of absolute errors for both translation and rotation parameters affirm the method’s stability and suitability, underscoring its effectiveness in consistently producing reliable and accurate estimates, regardless of the random components introduced during its execution.

4.1.5 Sensor to Board Distance

The impact of the distance between the LiDAR sensors and the calibration board on the calibration accuracy was investigated. To explore the optimal distance range for reliable pre-calibration, various sensor-to-board distances, ranging from 3 meters to 4.5 meters with 0.5-meter increments, were considered. The calibration results, presented in Table 4.9, demonstrate consistent performance across different distances, with only minute variations observed.

Figure 4.9: RMSE and MAE vs. distance between front LiDAR and the calibration board

Figure 4.9 visually portrays the relationship between RMSE, MAE, and the distance between the front LiDAR sensor and the calibration board. The plot clearly demonstrates that calibration errors remain relatively low when the distance falls within the range of 3 to 3.5 meters. Beyond this range, errors start to increase; however, they do not significantly compromise calibration accuracy. This finding underscores the robustness of the calibration algorithm to variations in sensor-to-board distance, while also highlighting that a distance of 3 to 3.5 meters is particularly well-suited for calibration purposes.

It is essential to maintain an appropriate distance, as it allows the calibration pattern to be detectable and recognizable by the sensor while ensuring that the calibration board remains visible.

Distance	Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
3.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: 0.0003 z: -1.0275 roll: 0.3905 pitch: -0.1606 yaw: 0.0486	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0003 z: 0.0055 roll: 0.3905 pitch: 0.1606 yaw: 0.0486	Translation: 0.0033 Rotation: 0.2454	Translation: 0.0024 Rotation: 0.1999	1.6966e-09	0.1148	0.0538
3.5	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4149 y: -0.0030 z: -1.0301 roll: -0.3747 pitch: -0.1482 yaw: 0.0250	x: 0.0019 y: 0.0030 z: 0.0029 roll: 0.3747 pitch: 0.1482 yaw: 0.0250	Translation: 0.0026 Rotation: 0.2331	Translation: 0.0026 Rotation: 0.1826	6.3196e-11	0.1034	0.0503
4.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4153 y: 0.0268 z: -1.0268 roll: 1.2831 pitch: -0.1227 yaw: -0.0052	x: 0.0023 y: 0.0268 z: 0.0062 roll: 1.2831 pitch: 0.1227 yaw: 0.0052	Translation: 0.0159 Rotation: 0.7442	Translation: 0.0118 Rotation: 0.4703	8.1503e-10	0.3463	0.1627
4.5	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4144 y: -0.0031 z: -1.0470 roll: 0.5053 pitch: -0.1284 yaw: 0.0173	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0031 z: 0.0140 roll: 0.5053 pitch: 0.1284 yaw: 0.0173	Translation: 0.0083 Rotation: 0.3012	Translation: 0.0062 Rotation: 0.2170	5.3457e-10	0.1393	0.0666

Table 4.9: Effect of distance between front LiDAR and the calibration board on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), Distance values, P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

4.1.6 Board to Wall Distance

Similarly, the distance between the calibration board and the wall was adjusted to examine its impact on calibration accuracy. This investigation helped identify the potential interference from the wall and its impact on calibration.

Figure 4.10: RMSE and MAE vs. distance between the wall and the calibration board values

The distance between the calibration board and the wall varied from 2 meters to 5 meters, with an increment of 1 meter. The corresponding calibration results are presented in Table 4.10. The plot in Figure 4.10 illustrates the variations in errors

for both rotation and translation values as the distance is changed. A spike in errors can be observed when the distance is 3 meters, possibly due to noise or data recording issues. However, consistent and gradual increases in errors are evident as the distance increases.

The findings indicate that the calibration results are better when the calibration board is closer to the wall. Empirical observations suggest that a distance of less than 2 meters between the wall and the calibration board results in smaller shadows of circular holes, which may again lead to issues during circle segmentation. Therefore, it is essential to strike a balance in the distance to the wall, ensuring that the shadows of the circular holes and the board edges are visible without being too close or too far.

Distance	Ground Truth	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
2.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4128 y: 0.0071 z: -1.0331 roll: 0.2168 pitch: 0.0202 yaw: -0.0943	x: 0.0002 y: 0.0071 z: 0.0001 roll: 0.2168 pitch: 0.0202 yaw: 0.0943	Translation: 0.0041 Rotation: 0.1370	Translation: 0.0025 Rotation: 0.1104	4.6753e-10	0.0667	0.0319
3.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4119 y: 0.0019 z: -1.0214 roll: -1.0197 pitch: 0.1179 yaw: -0.1085	x: 0.0011 y: 0.0019 z: 0.0116 roll: 1.0197 pitch: 0.1179 yaw: 0.1085	Translation: 0.0068 Rotation: 0.5959	Translation: 0.0049 Rotation: 0.4154	3.8226e-10	0.2720	0.1313
4.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4124 y: 0.0079 z: -1.0265 roll: -0.2538 pitch: 0.0722 yaw: -0.0959	x: 0.0006 y: 0.0079 z: 0.0065 roll: 0.2538 pitch: 0.0722 yaw: 0.0959	Translation: 0.0059 Rotation: 0.1621	Translation: 0.0050 Rotation: 0.1406	1.4831e-10	0.0826	0.0391
5.0	x: 2.4130 y: 0.0000 z: -1.0330 roll: 0.0000 pitch: 0.0000 yaw: 0.0000	x: 2.4120 y: 0.0158 z: -1.0117 roll: -0.2634 pitch: 0.1050 yaw: -0.1169	x: 0.0001 y: 0.0158 z: 0.0213 roll: 0.2634 pitch: 0.1050 yaw: 0.1169	Translation: 0.0153 Rotation: 0.1771	Translation: 0.0127 Rotation: 0.1618	3.2001e-10	0.0954	0.0464

Table 4.10: Effect of distance between the wall and the calibration board on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

4.1.7 Robustness to Noise

To investigate the robustness of the calibration method to noise, simulated noise was introduced into the LiDAR data using the CARLA simulator [6]. Several techniques could be employed to simulate noise; however, in this thesis, the parameter adjusted was the noise standard deviation. By controlling the level of noise through this parameter, different noise levels were achieved in the simulated LiDAR data. The primary objective of this experiment was to assess the impact of noise on the calibration process and evaluate the performance of the calibration method under noisy conditions.

In the analysis, the standard deviation parameter was incrementally varied from 0.01 to 0.11 meters, with an increment of 0.02 meters, and the results are presented

Figure 4.11: RMSE and MAE for translation and rotation vs. Noise Values

in Table 4.11. As the noise level increased, a decrease in calibration performance was observed. This decline can be attributed to the presence of outliers and a reduction in reliable data points within the noisy data. Consequently, critical steps such as plane segmentation, circle segmentation, and registration were affected, resulting in a decrease in calibration accuracy.

The plot in Figure 4.11 reveals that the calibration method is more sensitive to noise in rotation than in translation. As the noise standard deviation increases, the RMSE and MAE values for rotation show a more significant increase compared to those for translation. This suggests that the calibration accuracy is more susceptible to noise in the rotational components of the LiDAR data. Furthermore, Figure 4.12 illustrates that the SS, P2P, and P2N metrics demonstrate a gradual degradation in performance as the noise level rises. Higher noise levels introduce more outliers and data inconsistencies, leading to a decrease in the alignment quality between the master LiDAR and the slave LiDAR sensors.

Figure 4.12: SS, P2P, and P2N vs. Noise Values

The calibration methods were extensively evaluated using various metrics and pa-

parameter settings in a simulation environment. The collected data was meticulously analyzed to gain insights into the performance and limitations of the proposed method. These findings contribute to the development of an effective pre-calibration method for LiDAR sensors, enhancing their accuracy and reliability in real-world applications.

Noise value	Estimated	AE	RMSE	MAE	SS	P2P	P2N
0.01	x: 2.4162 y: 0.0027 z: -1.0436 roll: -0.3646 pitch: -0.2077 yaw: -0.0225	x: 0.0038 y: 0.0000 z: 0.0006 roll: 0.7293 pitch: 0.4154 yaw: 0.0449	Translation: 0.0066 Rotation: 0.2426	Translation: 0.0055 Rotation: 0.1983	1.0982e-10	0.1074	0.0518
0.03	x: 2.4183 y: 0.0027 z: -1.0430 roll: 0.5151 pitch: -0.2062 yaw: 0.0348	x: 0.0061 y: 0.0000 z: 0.0005 roll: 0.5150 pitch: 0.2062 yaw: 0.0348	Translation: 0.0067 Rotation: 0.3210	Translation: 0.0060 Rotation: 0.2520	1.8929e-09	0.1494	0.0719
0.05	x: 2.4181 y: 0.0281 z: -1.0331 roll: 0.5120 pitch: -0.1257 yaw: -0.2278	x: 0.0038 y: 0.0254 z: 0.0100 roll: 0.5120 pitch: 0.1257 yaw: 0.2278	Translation: 0.0165 Rotation: 0.3316	Translation: 0.0111 Rotation: 0.2885	5.7176e-10	0.1788	0.0819
0.07	x: 2.4375 y: -0.0064 z: -1.1358 roll: 0.3212 pitch: -1.3106 yaw: 0.1448	x: 0.0014 y: 0.0122 z: 0.0169 roll: 1.2724 pitch: 0.1318 yaw: 0.0224	Translation: 0.0121 Rotation: 0.7387	Translation: 0.0102 Rotation: 0.4755	4.3262e-10	0.3388	0.1602
0.09	x: 2.4277 y: -0.0883 z: -1.0829 roll: 0.4530 pitch: -0.7790 yaw: 1.2082	x: 0.0019 y: 0.0173 z: 0.0120 roll: 1.2835 pitch: 0.1582 yaw: 0.0073	Translation: 0.0122 Rotation: 0.7466	Translation: 0.0104 Rotation: 0.4830	1.6515e-09	0.3452	0.1655
0.11	x: 2.4408 y: -0.0990 z: -1.0576 roll: -0.2280 pitch: -0.7600 yaw: 1.3168	x: 0.0021 y: 0.0180 z: 0.0129 roll: 1.3872 pitch: 0.1677 yaw: 0.0076	Translation: 0.0122 Rotation: 0.7466	Translation: 0.0104 Rotation: 0.4830	1.5732e-10	0.3452	0.1655

Table 4.11: Effect of simulated noise on the calibration (all translation values (x, y, z, Translation), Noise values, P2P values are in meters, all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw, Rotation) are in degrees and SS, P2N values are dimensionless)

4.2 Real Data Experiments

Following the simulation experiments, the calibration algorithm was applied to real-world data collected from Project JUPITER. As mentioned in section 1.2, The JUPITER vehicle is equipped with LiDAR sensors mounted on the front, rear, and sides, with the Pandora sensor serving as the reference on the roof of the vehicle. Since the extrinsic transformation between the front-facing Livox LiDAR and the base frame of the vehicle is well-known, and the extrinsic transformations between

the Pandora and the other sensors, including the Livox LiDAR, can be calculated using the calibration algorithm, the extrinsic transformations of all other LiDARs with respect to the base frame can be deduced accordingly.

In the real-world experiments, the MRE metric [15] was employed to assess the accuracy of the calibration results, as mentioned in the section 3.5. By comparing the MRE values before and after calibration, the effectiveness of the algorithm in reducing disparities and improving alignment between the LiDAR point clouds could be evaluated. For this thesis, the target was to achieve MRE values of at least under 0.1 meters, which is considered acceptable, indicating accurate calibration results. Moreover, achieving MRE values under 0.05 meters was considered to be very acceptable, further enhancing the precision and reliability of the calibration.

4.2.1 Initial Calibration

Following the guidelines outlined in the section 3.4.2, rosbags were recorded for each combination of sensors with the reference LiDAR, Pandora. For each combination, 4 to 5 positions were recorded. However, certain positions were discarded before running the calibration due to factors such as incorrect board positioning, excessive hand movement, improper board alignment, or other issues. The calibration results for the front, rear, right, and left side LiDARs with respect to the Pandora sensor [32] are presented in the table 4.12, along with the estimated extrinsic transformation and the corresponding MRE.

Sensor To Sensor	X (m)	Y (m)	Z (m)	Roll (degrees)	Pitch (degrees)	Yaw (degrees)	MRE Before Calibration (m)	MRE After Calibration (m)
Pandora Frame to Front Livox	2.8974	0.1077	-1.0535	-2.4800	1.1830	-3.8286	1.1034	0.0369
							1.0526	0.0340
							1.1290	0.0386
Pandora Frame to Rear Livox	-1.9251	0.1426	-1.1300	2.9056	0.2583	174.6072	0.4797	0.0442
							0.4352	0.0435
							0.4665	0.0468
Pandora Frame to Right Livox	0.2907	-0.9872	-1.5481	0.2896	-1.6095	-94.7875	0.5075	0.0947
							0.4614	0.0906
							0.4642	0.0937
Pandora Frame to Left Livox	0.3512	0.7991	-1.5364	-0.3029	3.2740	85.2437	1.5645	0.5891
							1.4503	0.5887
							1.5335	0.5896

Table 4.12: Initial calibration results of the real-world data (all translation values (X, Y, Z), MRE values are in meters, and all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw) are in degrees)

The MRE values for the front and rear LiDARs fall within the range of 0.04 meters, which is considered very acceptable, indicating precise and accurate calibration results. However, for the side LiDARs, the MRE values are relatively high, suggesting issues with the calibration results.

Analysis reveals two possible reasons for these discrepancies. Firstly, the Pandora sensor has dense channels in the center, while the channels on the top and bottom are widely spread, resulting in sparse regions as shown in Figure 4.13. The height difference between the top Pandora and side sensors leads to a narrow overlap FOV area, necessitating the placement of the calibration board at a greater distance from

the car to ensure it is within the overlapping area of the sensors. However, primarily placing the calibration board in the sparse region of the Pandora sensor based on the sensor positions results in only 2 or 3 channels of Pandora passing through the circle centers. This boundary condition poses a challenge for the calibration algorithm, leading to inaccurate calibration. Secondly, due to the same reason, most recorded positions are discarded as the board is not placed in the narrow overlap area. For the right sensor, only 3 possible positions were selected, while for the left sensor, only 1 position was utilized, thereby reducing the accuracy of the calibration for this sensor combination. In contrast, for the front and rear LiDARs, 4 positions were selected, resulting in higher calibration accuracy.

Figure 4.13: Point cloud density distribution of Pandora LiDAR: Dense channels at the center, sparse channels at the top and bottom.

4.2.2 Optimization: Re-Calibration

To address the challenges mentioned in the previous section 4.2.1 and enhance the calibration accuracy for the side LiDARs, an optimization step, as explained in section 3.2.4, is performed after the initial calibration. The MRE is calculated before calibration, after the initial calibration, and after the optimization step, providing insights into the effectiveness of the optimization process. The optimization significantly improves the calibration accuracy for both the right and left LiDARs, resulting in reduced MRE values.

After the optimization, the MRE for the right LiDAR decreases from 0.09 meters to 0.04 meters, indicating an improvement of 55.6% compared to the previous step and an impressive 91.1% improvement in total compared to before calibration. Similarly, for the left LiDAR, the MRE reduces from 0.6 meters to 0.09 meters after the optimization, representing an 85% improvement compared to the previous step and a remarkable 94% improvement in total compared to before calibration. These improvements can be visualized in Figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14: Improvement in calibration results after re-calibration (Optimization)

Sensor To Sensor	X (m)	Y (m)	Z (m)	Roll (degrees)	Pitch (degrees)	Yaw (degrees)	MRE Before Calibration (m)	MRE After Initial Calibration (m)	MRE After Re-Calibration (m) (Optimization)
Pandora Frame to Front Livox	2.9551	0.1138	-1.0992	-3.2912	1.1933	-6.1819	1.1034 1.0526 1.1290	0.0369 0.0340 0.0386	0.0382 0.0392 0.0363
Pandora Frame to Rear Livox	-1.9310	0.0507	-1.1328	2.9245	0.2847	174.0334	0.4797 0.4352 0.4665	0.0442 0.0435 0.0468	0.0485 0.0432 0.0473
Pandora Frame to Right Livox	0.2476	-0.9738	-1.4248	0.0047	-0.4550	-94.6127	0.5075 0.4614 0.4642	0.0947 0.0906 0.0937	0.0458 0.0430 0.0496
Pandora Frame to Left Livox	0.2815	0.8945	-1.5371	-1.9366	4.4175	85.1530	1.5645 1.4503 1.5335	0.5891 0.5887 0.5896	0.0812 0.0862 0.0843

Table 4.13: Improved calibration results of the real-world data after re-calibration (all translation values (X, Y, Z), MRE values are in meters, and all rotation values (roll, pitch, yaw) are in degrees)

These reduced MRE values demonstrate significantly improved calibration accuracy for both the right and left LiDARs, ensuring precise and accurate calibration results. Table 4.13 presents the new calibration results obtained after optimization, along with the resulting MREs. The optimization step aims to refine the calibration estimate and mitigate the impact of sparse regions and limited overlapping Field of View (FOV) areas on the side LiDARs' calibration accuracy.

However, it is essential to highlight that further improvements in calibration accuracy for the left LiDAR can be achieved by collecting more valid calibration data. Increasing the quantity and diversity of calibration data can positively influence the calibration quality and overall performance of the algorithm. A comprehensive analysis of the detailed results from these experiments, along with potential strategies

for enhancing the calibration process, will be presented in the next section 4.2.3, which covers the study of the effect of the number of poses on calibration.

The results showcase the effectiveness of the optimization step in fine-tuning the calibration and achieving highly accurate and reliable calibration results for both the right and left LiDAR sensors. The optimization process plays a crucial role in addressing calibration challenges and significantly enhancing calibration accuracy, leading to precise and aligned point clouds for subsequent perception tasks.

4.2.3 Impact of Number of Poses

The impact of the number of positions on calibration accuracy was already studied using simulation data in section 4.1.3, which clearly demonstrated that as the number of poses increased, the calibration accuracy improved. To further investigate and reach the same conclusion using real data, additional experimentation was conducted using the real data collected for the calibration of the right LiDAR.

Number of Poses	MRE (m)
1	0.2765
2	0.1859
3	0.1380
4	0.0947

Table 4.14: Effect of number of calibration poses on MRE for the right LiDAR sensor in real-world data (MRE values are in meters)

The calibration process was repeated multiple times, varying the number of calibration positions from 1 to 4, and the Mean Registration Error (MRE) results for each configuration were recorded and tabulated in Table 4.14. The analysis demonstrated a gradual decrease in the MRE as the number of positions used for calibration increased. For example, with only one pose used for calibration, the MRE was measured at 0.2765 meters. However, as the number of calibration poses increased to four, the MRE reduced to 0.0947 meters, representing a considerable 66% improvement in calibration accuracy, as clearly visualized in Figure 4.15. These findings are consistent with the results obtained from the simulation data (Table 4.7), where an increase in the number of positions led to improved calibration accuracy.

These results clearly indicate that each additional pose contributes significantly to refining the calibration estimate and achieving a higher level of accuracy. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to use a sufficient number of calibration poses to achieve the desired level of accuracy in the calibration process. However, it is essential to strike a practical balance between the number of calibration poses and the desired calibration accuracy, considering factors such as data collection time and computational resources. The rate of improvement starts to level off as the number of poses goes beyond 4 or 5 poses, and the improvement becomes minor. Therefore, careful consideration should be given to selecting an optimal number of poses that provide the desired calibration accuracy without incurring unnecessary resource costs.

Figure 4.15: Effect of number of calibration poses on MRE for the right LiDAR sensor in real-world data (MRE values are in meters)

The real-world experiments provided practical insights into the algorithm’s performance under real-world conditions, considering environmental factors and real sensor characteristics. These experiments demonstrated the algorithm’s capability to pre-calibrate LiDAR sensors accurately, providing reliable and aligned point clouds for subsequent perception tasks.

4.3 Results and Discussion

The simulation experiments have provided valuable insights into the calibration process and its performance. Several important points have been observed and discussed:

Optimal Sensor Distances and Orientations: The calibration process yields better results when the relative X distance between the sensors is in the range of 3 to 3.2 meters, and the relative Y and Z distances are as close to zero as possible. Similarly, calibration results are most accurate when the relative rotation in all three directions (roll, pitch, and yaw) is around zero, indicating that such sensor configurations result in better calibration.

Effect of Calibration Poses: Increasing the number of calibration poses has a positive impact on calibration accuracy. More calibration poses enhances calibration accuracy and reduce the MRE between the point clouds.

Optimal Distances: The optimal distance for the sensors to the calibration board is found to be around 3 to 3.5 meters, while the optimal distance for the calibration board to the wall is approximately 2 meters. These distances ensure a clear and sufficient FOV overlap, which is critical for accurate calibration.

Impact of Noise: The simulation results demonstrate that increasing the noise in the simulation data negatively affects calibration accuracy. Higher noise levels lead to decreased precision in the calibration process and can introduce errors in the estimated sensor poses. Therefore, it is essential to minimize noise in the data acquisition process to achieve more reliable and accurate calibration outcomes.

Influence of Randomization Steps: The study also indicates that the calibration algorithm is not significantly influenced by randomization steps like RANSAC and circle segmentation. This suggests that the calibration process remains robust and consistent despite random variations introduced during these steps.

Figure 4.16: Calibration results: Overlapping of calibration boards from two LiDAR sensors - Before and after calibration

Based on these findings, real-world experiments are conducted using ROS bags collected from the JUPITER platform. The calibration results obtained from the real-world data yield significant outcomes. The MRE values for the calibration of front and rear LiDARs with Pandora fall within the acceptable range of 0.04 meters (as mentioned in section 4.2), indicating precise and accurate calibration results. The MRE values before calibration (Figure 4.16(a)) show a range of 1 meter, whereas after calibration (Figure 4.16(b)), the MRE decreases to 0.04 meters, highlighting the importance and reliability of calibration. These results are also summarized in Table 4.13.

Similar improvements in the calibration of the front LiDAR can be observed in Figures 4.17(a), 4.17(b), 4.18(a), and 4.18(b), where the point clouds are correctly aligned after calibration. In figure 4.17(a), there is a noticeable shift in the point cloud for a pole, the calibration board, and the wall behind it. However, in figure 4.17(b), they are properly aligned with no visible shift.

During data collection, two individuals hold the board in front of a wall. In Figure 4.19(a), the white point cloud representing the Pandora sensor cloud and the red point cloud representing the Livox sensor cloud shows a significant distance between the two individuals, with a visible shift of approximately 1 meter. After calibration, as shown in Figure 4.19(b), proper alignment is achieved for the two people in both

Figure 4.17: Calibration results: Pole, calibration board, and wall - Before and after calibration

Figure 4.18: Calibration results: Top view of LiDAR point clouds - Before and after calibration

point clouds. Similar improvements can be observed for a person crossing the vehicle path in Figures 4.20(a) and 4.20(b).

On the other hand, the MRE values for the side LiDARs exhibit relatively higher values, indicating issues with calibration accuracy. The right LiDAR has an MRE of approximately 9 centimeters, while the left LiDAR ranges from 55 to 60 centimeters, significantly higher. Table 4.12 presents the initial calibration results. These calibration results are deemed unusable, necessitating further analysis to identify the underlying causes and develop appropriate remedies.

Figures 4.21(a) and 4.21(b) provide a comprehensive 360-degree view of the point cloud from a top perspective, where the shifts that are visible before calibration are almost eliminated after calibration. From nearby poles, walls, and the calibration board to the farthest buildings, compound walls, and poles, it can be observed that the shift is greatly minimized after calibration. Although the high MRE values for the left LiDAR may not be as visible in this zoomed-out view after calibration, they are present in the range of 0.5 - 0.6 meters.

Figure 4.19: Calibration results: Two individuals holding the calibration board - Before and after calibration

Figure 4.20: Calibration results: Person crossing the vehicle path - Before and after calibration

As mentioned in section 4.2.1, the high MRE values for the side LiDARs, particularly the left one, can be attributed to two potential reasons. Firstly, the algorithm itself faced challenges due to difficult data conditions and limited overlapping FOV areas. Secondly, the number of valid poses used for the calibration affected the accuracy, with only 3 possible positions selected for the right sensor and 1 position utilized for the left sensor, reducing the calibration accuracy for this particular sensor combination.

To address the first issue and improve calibration accuracy, an optimization technique described in detail in section 3.2.4 is employed. This optimization step involves re-calibrating the algorithm after the initial calibration to further optimize

Figure 4.21: Calibration results: 360 surround top view - Before and after calibration

the results. Table 4.13 presents the calibration results after the optimization is performed. The optimization significantly enhances the calibration accuracy for the side LiDARs, resulting in reduced MRE values by a factor of 2 for the right LiDARs and by a factor of 6 for the left LiDARs, bringing them to a scale of under 0.1 meters. For the right LiDAR, the MRE decreases from 0.09 meters to 0.04 meters, which is considered accurate and acceptable. Furthermore, for the left LiDAR, a substantial improvement is observed as the MRE decreases from 0.5 or 0.6 meters to 0.09 meters. Considering that only 1 position was initially considered for the left LiDAR calibration, these results are already promising.

However, with the addition of further positions for the left LiDAR calibration, addressing the second issue, the MRE can potentially be further reduced to the range of 0.04 meters. This possibility was demonstrated through a study on the effect of the number of valid poses used for calibration on the accuracy of the calibration results, as explained in section 4.2.3.

As a result, all the LiDARs are effectively calibrated, with MRE values ranging within 4 centimeters, except for the left LiDAR, which currently stands at around 9 centimeters. However, it has been shown that further improvements can be achieved with additional data collection.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this master thesis, the primary focus is on addressing the critical problem of accurately calibrating LiDAR sensors in a multi-LiDAR sensor system, which is essential for reliable perception and decision-making in autonomous vehicles. The proposed *Velo2cam* Extrinsic Calibration Method was adapted as explained in section 3.2 and thoroughly analyzed through simulation and real-world experiments to calibrate the extrinsic parameters between each LiDAR sensor and a master LiDAR, establishing the relative transformations between them.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The simulation experiments highlight the importance of maintaining appropriate distances and orientations between the sensors to be calibrated, the calibration board, and the wall to achieve a clear and wide FOV overlap. This is crucial for the calibration algorithm [4] and leads to highly precise results, unaffected by randomization steps like RANSAC and circle segmentation.

Both simulation and real-world data support the finding that increasing the number of calibration poses improves accuracy by reducing the MRE between point clouds. Real-world data obtained from ROS bags on the JUPITER platform validate the significance of the calibration results. The MRE values for front and rear LiDAR calibration with Pandora fall within the acceptable range of 4 centimeters, indicating precise and accurate calibration. The algorithm effectively aligns objects, eliminating shifts and enhancing overall accuracy.

However, the side LiDARs exhibit relatively higher MRE values, indicating accuracy issues. Through further analysis, an optimization technique has been proposed and applied to address these calibration issues. The optimization process involves re-calibrating the algorithm using filtered source and target point clouds, removing outliers based on an MRE threshold, which improves calibration accuracy. Consequently, the MRE values for the side LiDARs are significantly reduced, indicating accurate and acceptable calibration.

The calibration algorithm demonstrates effective calibration for all LiDARs, with MRE values ranging within 4 centimeters, except for the left LiDAR, which currently stands at approximately 9 centimeters. However, it has been identified that this discrepancy is due to a lack of data, and collecting additional data can further enhance the calibration accuracy for the left LiDAR.

5.2 Limitations and Potential Areas for Improvement

During the calibration process, certain limitations were identified, highlighting potential areas for improvement. One limitation pertains to the accuracy of the calibration results for the left LiDAR, which were less precise compared to the other LiDARs. This limitation can be attributed to the selection of only one position from all the recordings, resulting in insufficient data. To enhance the accuracy specifically for the left LiDAR, it is recommended to record multiple positions of the calibration board.

Another limitation arises from the oscillation or movement of the calibration board during the data recording process, as it was held by two individuals. This setup is prone to errors and vibrations, leading to the exclusion of numerous recorded positions. To mitigate this limitation, a potential solution would involve developing a mechanical stand or an adjustable device that provides stability and allows for recording multiple positions of the calibration board without any movement.

Further improvements can be made to the calibration algorithm to enhance its performance with sparse point clouds. The current algorithm faces challenges when the density of the point cloud decreases, making the circle segmentation task more difficult. It is crucial to investigate and develop strategies to address this limitation, ensuring robustness even with sparse point clouds.

To address the non-overlapping area between the LiDAR sensor point clouds, an alternative solution considered is the use of a bridge sensor. Instead of relying solely on the LiDAR sensor as a bridge sensor, exploring the use of a camera, stereo camera, or other sensor modalities as a bridge sensor may potentially further improve the calibration accuracy. For this reason, it is recommendable to carry out a comparison study among these different alternatives. Another option considered but not tested is the utilization of an external sensor facing the ego car as a bridge sensor, sharing a common FOV with the two LiDARs to be calibrated and the calibration board.

Additionally, a more comprehensive study is required to examine the impact of LiDAR scan patterns on calibration accuracy. Although some progress has been made in developing sensor models for the Blickfeld and Livox sensors in the simulation environment, the research could not be continued due to internal pipeline issues in the simulation engine development and time constraints of the Master Thesis. Further research in this area will contribute to improving the robustness and accuracy of the calibration.

As new automatic targetless methods are being researched, adapting the algorithm to perform without specific targets and utilizing the natural geometry in the environment could be a significant improvement. However, caution must be exercised to ensure that the performance of the model is not compromised. Deep learning-based models should also be evaluated, and a comprehensive comparative study should be conducted to assess their effectiveness.

Furthermore, the study using simulation data can be extended further by including a larger number of points to assess the impact of point density on calibration accuracy. Investigating the effect of the number of non-coplanar poses on calibration

accuracy would also provide valuable insights into the algorithm's performance under different pose configurations. Additionally, studying the impact of the drop-off rates parameter while evaluating the robustness to noise on calibration accuracy would be beneficial in understanding how the algorithm handles noisy data.

The existing performance metrics, including RMSE, AE, MAE, MRE, Similarity score, P2P, and P2N, provide valuable insights into calibration accuracy, alignment, and robustness. Additionally, incorporating additional metrics like Cross-Calibration Performance and Calibration Stability can further enhance the evaluation process. Cross-Calibration Performance specifically assesses the calibration consistency among lidar sensors in multi-lidar systems, ensuring accurate alignment across sensors. On the other hand, Calibration Stability evaluates the algorithm's robustness under changing environmental conditions. By considering these metrics both with and without ground truth data, a comprehensive performance assessment can be achieved, providing a thorough evaluation of the calibration algorithm's effectiveness and reliability.

In conclusion, the developed method for pre-calibrating LiDAR sensors based on a simulation environment demonstrates promising results. However, addressing the identified limitations and pursuing the suggested areas for improvement will enhance the overall calibration accuracy and robustness.

Bibliography

- [1] *An-Introduction-to-Automotive-LIDAR*. <https://www.scribd.com/document/481425544/An-Introduction-to-Automotive-LIDAR-Rev-A>.
- [2] K. S. Arun; T. S. Huang; S. D. Blostein. „Least-Squares Fitting of Two 3-D Point Sets“. In: vol. PAMI-9. 5. 1987, pp. 698–700. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.1987.4767965.
- [3] Jorge Beltrán et al. „Towards Autonomous Driving: a Multi-Modal 360° Perception Proposal“. In: *CoRR* abs/2008.09672 (2020).
- [4] Jorge Beltrán et al. „Automatic Extrinsic Calibration Method for LiDAR and Camera Sensor Setups“. In: vol. 23. Oct. 2022, pp. 1–13. DOI: 10.1109/TITS.2022.3155228.
- [5] Yury Blokhinov et al. „Automatic Calibration of Multiple Cameras and Lidars for Autonomous Vehicles“. In: vol. 45. June 2021, pp. 382–393. DOI: 10.18287/2412-6179-C0-812.
- [6] *CARLA Simulator*. https://carla.org/solutions/face_mesh/.
- [7] Siheng Chen et al. „3D Point Cloud Processing and Learning for Autonomous Driving“. In: *CoRR* abs/2003.00601 (2020).
- [8] Y. Chen; G. Medioni. „Object Modeling by Registration of Multiple Range Images“. In: *Proceedings. 1991 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. 1991, 2724–2729 vol.3. DOI: 10.1109/ROBOT.1991.132043.
- [9] Dong-Geol Choi et al. „Extrinsic Calibration of 2-D Lidars Using Two Orthogonal Planes“. In: vol. 32. 1. 2016, pp. 83–98. DOI: 10.1109/TR0.2015.2502860.
- [10] Jorge Beltrán de la Cita. „Multimodal Perception for Autonomous Driving“. PhD thesis. Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, 2022.
- [11] Sandipan Das et al. „Extrinsic Calibration and Verification of Multiple Non-overlapping Field of View Lidar Sensors“. In: *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/icra46639.2022.9811704. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icra46639.2022.9811704>.

- [12] Stefano Debattisti; Luca Mazzei; Matteo Panciroli. „Automated Extrinsic Laser and Camera Inter-Calibration using Triangular Targets“. In: *2013 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*. 2013, pp. 696–701. DOI: 10.1109/IVS.2013.6629548.
- [13] Ankit Dhall et al. „LiDAR-Camera Calibration using 3D-3D Point correspondences“. In: *CoRR* abs/1705.09785 (2017).
- [14] Klaus Dietmayer; Stephan Reuter; Dominik Nuss. „Representation of Fused Environment Data“. In: Jan. 2016, pp. 567–603. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-12352-3_25.
- [15] *Evaluating the Accuracy of Single Camera Calibration*. <https://de.mathworks.com/help/vision/ug/evaluating-the-accuracy-of-single-camera-calibration.html>.
- [16] Chuan Fang et al. „Single-Shot is Enough: Panoramic Infrastructure Based Calibration of Multiple Cameras and 3D LiDARs“. In: (2021).
- [17] Di Feng et al. „Deep Multi-modal Object Detection and Semantic Segmentation for Autonomous Driving: Datasets, Methods, and Challenges“. In: vol. abs/1902.07830. 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TITS.2020.2972974. arXiv: 1902.07830. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.07830>.
- [18] Martin A. Fischler; Robert C. Bolles. „Random Sample Consensus: A Paradigm for Model Fitting with Applications to Image Analysis and Automated Cartography“. In: vol. 24. 1981, pp. 381–395. DOI: 10.1145/358669.358692.
- [19] Sergio Garrido-Jurado et al. „Automatic Generation and Detection of Highly Reliable Fiducial Markers under Occlusion“. In: vol. 47. June 2014, 2280–2292. DOI: 10.1016/j.patcog.2014.01.005.
- [20] Andreas Geiger et al. „Automatic Camera and Range Sensor Calibration using a Single Shot“. In: 2012, pp. 3936–3943. DOI: 10.1109/ICRA.2012.6224570.
- [21] Yulan Guo et al. „3D Object Recognition in Cluttered Scenes with Local Surface Features: A Survey“. In: vol. 36. 11. 2014, pp. 2270–2287. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2014.2316828.
- [22] Richard Hartley; Andrew Zisserman. „Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision“. In: Cambridge University Press, 2004. DOI: 10.1017/CB09780511811685.
- [23] Mengwen He et al. „Pairwise LIDAR Calibration using Multi-type 3D Geometric Features in Natural Scene“. In: *2013 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. 2013, pp. 1828–1835. DOI: 10.1109/IRoS.2013.6696597.

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- [24] Heiko Hirschmuller. „Stereo Processing by Semiglobal Matching and Mutual Information“. In: vol. 30. 2. 2008, pp. 328–341. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2007.1166.
- [25] Radu Horaud; Fadi Dornaika. „Hand-Eye Calibration“. In: vol. 14. 3. 1995, pp. 195–210. DOI: 10.1177/027836499501400301. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1177/027836499501400301>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1177/027836499501400301>.
- [26] Xiaoshui Huang et al. „A Comprehensive Survey on Point Cloud Registration“. In: *CoRR* abs/2103.02690 (2021).
- [27] *K-D Trees*. <https://dev.to/ahmedelgohary1/k-d-trees-3k3h>.
- [28] Jesse Levinson; Sebastian Thrun. „Automatic Online Calibration of Cameras and Lasers“. In: *Robotics: Science and Systems*. 2013.
- [29] Enrique Marti et al. „A Review of Sensor Technologies for Perception in Automated Driving“. In: vol. 11. 4. 2019, pp. 94–108. DOI: 10.1109/MITS.2019.2907630.
- [30] Mingyan Nie et al. „Automatic Extrinsic Calibration of Dual LiDARs With Adaptive Surface Normal Estimation“. In: vol. 72. 2023, pp. 1–11. DOI: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3229714.
- [31] *Organized and Unorganized Point Clouds*. <https://de.mathworks.com/help/lidar/ug/organized-and-unorganized-point-clouds.html>.
- [32] *Pandora-Users-Manual*. <https://www.symphotony.com/wp-content/uploads/20181015-Pandora-Users-Manual.pdf>.
- [33] Yoonsu Park et al. „Calibration between Color Camera and 3D LIDAR Instruments with a Polygonal Planar Board“. In: vol. 14. 2014, pp. 5333–5353. DOI: 10.3390/s140305333.
- [34] *PCL Point Cloud Library - PCD File Format*. https://pcl.readthedocs.io/projects/tutorials/en/pcl-1.12.1/pcd_file_format.html.
- [35] Christopher V. Poulton et al. „Optical Phased Arrays for Integrated Beam Steering“. In: *2018 IEEE 15th International Conference on Group IV Photonics (GFP)*. 2018, pp. 1–2. DOI: 10.1109/GROUP4.2018.8478729.
- [36] Thinal Raj et al. „A Survey on LiDAR Scanning Mechanisms“. In: vol. 9. 5. 2020. DOI: 10.3390/electronics9050741. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/9/5/741>.

- [37] Radu Bogdan Rusu; Steve Cousins. „3D is here: Point Cloud Library (PCL)“. In: *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. 2011, pp. 1–4. DOI: 10.1109/ICRA.2011.5980567.
- [38] Davide Scaramuzza; Ahad Harati; Roland Y. Siegwart. „Extrinsic Self Calibration of a Camera and a 3D Laser Range Finder from Natural Scenes“. In: 2007, pp. 4164–4169. DOI: 10.1109/IR0S.2007.4399276.
- [39] *Shan Liu u. a. 3D Point Cloud Analysis*. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-89180-0>.
- [40] Bastian Steder et al. „Point Feature Extraction on 3D Range Scans Taking into Account Object Boundaries“. In: *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. 2011, pp. 2601–2608. DOI: 10.1109/ICRA.2011.5980187.
- [41] S. Umeyama. „Least-Squares Estimation of Transformation Parameters between Two Point Patterns“. In: vol. 13. 4. 1991, pp. 376–380. DOI: 10.1109/34.88573.
- [42] *Understanding Wavelength Choice in LiDAR Systems*. <https://www.embedded.com/understanding-wavelength-choice-in-lidar-systems/>.
- [43] *Unique Signatures of Histograms for Local Surface Description*. <http://www.vision.deis.unibo.it/fede/papers/eccv10.pdf>.
- [44] Pengjin Wei et al. „CROON: Automatic Multi-LiDAR Calibration and Refinement Method in Road Scene“. In: *2022 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. 2022, pp. 12857–12863. DOI: 10.1109/IR0S47612.2022.9981558.
- [45] Hermann Winner et al. „Handbook of Driver Assistance Systems: Basic Information, Components and Systems for Active Safety and Comfort“. In: Jan. 2015, pp. 1–1602. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-12352-3.
- [46] Shan Wu et al. „NetCalib: A Novel Approach for LiDAR-Camera Auto-calibration Based on Deep Learning“. In: *2020 25th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)*. 2021, pp. 6648–6655. DOI: 10.1109/ICPR48806.2021.9412653.
- [47] Tao Wu et al. „Detailed Analysis on Generating the Range Image for LiDAR Point Cloud Processing“. In: vol. 10. 11. 2021. DOI: 10.3390/electronics10111224. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/10/11/1224>.
- [48] M.A. Zaiter et al. „3D LiDAR Extrinsic Calibration Method using Ground Plane Model Estimation“. In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Con-*

- nected Vehicles and Expo (ICCVE)*. 2019, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/ICCVE45908.2019.8964949.
- [49] Yu Zhong. „Intrinsic Shape Signatures: A Shape Descriptor for 3D Object Recognition“. In: *2009 IEEE 12th International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops, ICCV Workshops*. 2009, pp. 689–696. DOI: 10.1109/ICCVW.2009.5457637.
- [50] Lipu Zhou; Zimo Li; Michael Kaess. „Automatic Extrinsic Calibration of a Camera and a 3D LiDAR Using Line and Plane Correspondences“. In: *2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. 2018, pp. 5562–5569. DOI: 10.1109/IROS.2018.8593660.

